

DEATH OF AN AMERICAN CITY:
THE ROLE OF CAPITALISM IN URBAN DECAY

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This study examines the role that capitalism, as an economic process, plays in perpetuating urban decay within the city limits of Cincinnati, Ohio. The historical development of capitalism and urban growth is traced starting in early modern Europe and is concluded in late 20th century America. Using an integrated theoretical model based in classical conflict theory and ecological theories of community development, the spatial manifestations of economic, social, and ecological patterns are analyzed. Using Marx's Theory of Land Rent as a starting point, David Harvey's neo-Marxian geographical perspective is incorporated to provide theoretical linkage between variable dimensions. Various economic, social/demographic, and ecological variables were collected from the 2000 general Census, and categorized into their corresponding dimension. The analysis was split into 2 phases with each phase being analyzed separately and a general analysis was conducted on both together.

The spatial phase of analysis revealed that pockets of poverty, unemployment, lower household incomes, and other variables associated with urban decay, were not found to be clustered within the inner city as traditional suburbanization processes

would suggest. Rather, neighborhoods with a disproportionately higher number of residents with these characteristics are often located along the outer city limits, and are often adjacent to transportation corridors and Brownfield areas. The correlational analysis provided statistical validation to the spatial patterns. Each dimension was correlated independently, as well as cross-dimensionally, yielding consistent results with the spatial analysis, along and across dimensional lines, in both strength and direction. Using this type of theoretical and analytical structure, it can be concluded that capitalism, as an economic system, plays a crucial role in creating and maintaining pockets of urban decay within the city limits of Cincinnati, Ohio.

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Table of Contents

Chapter 1 Historical Background.....	1
The Industrial Revolution, the Rise of the Urban Environment, and the Emergence of Capitalism.....	1
The City of Cincinnati, Ohio.....	18
Chapter 2 Theoretical Perspectives.....	21
Marxian Economics.....	21
The Ecological Approach.....	30
The Role of Capitalism in Urban Decay.....	44
Material Exploitation.....	47
Social Exploitation.....	58
Political Exploitation.....	63
Theoretical Linkage.....	66
Economic Hypotheses.....	69
Social/Demographic Hypotheses.....	70
Ecological Hypothesis.....	71
Cross-dimensional Hypotheses.....	72
Chapter 3 Methods and Results.....	73
Spatial Analysis.....	74
Correlational Analysis.....	75
Results.....	76
Spatial: Economic.....	76
Spatial: Social/Demographic.....	77

Spatial: Ecological.....	77
Spatial: Cross-dimensional.....	79
Correlational Analysis.....	79
Economic Correlations.....	79
Social/Demographic Correlations.....	80
Ecological Correlations.....	80
Cross-dimensional Correlations.....	81
Chapter 4 Discussion and Conclusion.....	82
Economic Dimension.....	82
Social/Demographic Dimension.....	83
Ecological Dimension.....	84
Cross-dimensional.....	85
General Discussion.....	85
Limitations, Implications of the Data, and Future Research.....	86
Conclusion.....	87
References.....	90
Appendix.....	95

CHAPTER 1:
THE INDUSTRIAL REVOLUTION, THE RISE OF THE URBAN
ENVIRONMENT, AND THE EMERGANCE OF CAPITALISM

Prior to the Neolithic revolution around 10,000 BCE or earlier, individuals were mainly hunters and gatherers. The Neolithic revolution saw the development of agriculture, which made denser human populations possible, thereby supporting stable encampments, the forerunner to city development. The increased population density encouraged by farming and the increased output of food per unit of land, created conditions that seem more suitable for permanent city-like settlements. This centralization of the population made possible the existence of permanent settlements, the precursor of the modern urban environment; however, in order to fully understand the development of urban areas and the rise of capitalist economies, it is important to take brief look at the history of economic development, starting in early modern Europe.

The Early Modern period of European history spanned approximately 300 years, from roughly 1500 to 1800 a.d. This period was characterized by a cultural shift from theology to science, rapid technological progress, secularized civic politics through the development of the nation state, and the falling of feudalism. Among the developments in this time period was the rise of the economic system of merchantilism, in which capitalism has its earliest roots. Merchantilism consisted of economic capital (in the form of gold or silver) held by the state, with emphasis

placed on trade with other nations as a means of maintaining and increasing that wealth and increased military campaigns to protect the trade networks and interests in foreign lands. The first large-scale capitalist enterprises in industry, particularly mining, were financed and controlled by merchants, and this could be shown for the South-German mining industry of the fifteenth and sixteenth centuries (Banaji 2007:48).

Jakob Strieder's (1914) book *Studien zur Geschichte Kapitalistischer Organisationsformen* presents three noteworthy ideas: "first, that the mining industry played a seminal role in the evolution of modern capitalism; second, that merchants *created* large enterprises, that is, involved themselves in the organization of production and industry; and, finally, the more general thesis that commercial capitalism lay at the origin of the so-called capitalist spirit several centuries earlier, in Venice, Florence and other centers of 'early capitalism'" (Banaji 2007:48). In a later article, Strieder argues that "in a whole series of industries (woolen goods, silk weaving, linen export and metal industries), the merchant who organized the export trade, and made advances in one form or another to the workman, gained control over industries which had previously been in the hands of independent craftsmen" (Strieder 1929:3).

The years between 1500 and 1800 saw tremendous expansion of commercial, cultural, and biological exchanges around the world with the development of new long distance sea routes linking Europe with sub-Saharan Africa and the maritime networks of the Indian Ocean and East Asia (Bulliet et al. 2006:361). The discovery

of the Americas in the late 1400's and its bountiful resources helped to drive the mercantile economy of Europe through trade across the Atlantic and exploitation of the Native Americans and their resources.

Advances in scientific thought throughout this period questioned everything from agricultural methods to laws, religion, and social hierarchies in a movement now known as the Enlightenment (Bulliet et al. 2006:372). European society during this time was structured in a hierarchy based on power and access to resources. At the top of the social ladder were a relatively small number of noble families who dominated high offices in the church, government, and military and enjoyed special privileges such as tax exemptions; followed by merchants who had acquired wealth, but held no special privileges; meanwhile, at the bottom of the hierarchy were the mostly rural masses, peasants and laborers, with as many as 25 different social categories in between (Bulliet et al. 2006:372).

Upward mobility was possible, principally in the middle classes, and all but certainly this mobility was taking place in growing cities with the economy acting as the engine of change. "The expanding economy benefited members of the emerging merchant elite and their political allies, but most Europeans became worse off as prices rose [to finance trade and wars] faster than wages" (Bulliet et al. 2006:385).

The discovery of the Americas provided the nobles of Europe with another source of vast resources and the colonization of the eastern North American seaboard provided numerous trade pathways across the Atlantic, which came to be known as the Atlantic system, moving people and cultures, as well as goods and wealth (Bulliet

et al. 2006:388). These new colonists, who brought with them their social, political, and economic practices from the old world, searched for alternatives to the repressive nature of European imperialist control. America's unique natural setting was ideal for growth: the Atlantic Ocean protected it from war obsessive Europe, while providing access to major trade routes; it had a storehouse of natural wealth waiting to be utilized; a system of inland waterways, and a benign topography rendered the penetration of the continent from the east coast practicable; and it had a climate suitable for agricultural production (Schweinitz 1964:130-131).

Early on, the colonists adopted communal ownership of land and property as a means to shed their "old world" ways. "The absence of property rights, [one of the cornerstones of capitalism] destroys the work ethic and leads ultimately to starvation. After the securing of private property rights, the settlers began trading with the Native Americans and exploiting their comparative advantages" (Vance 2005:83) in order to better their situations.

The North American colonial empires of England and France, along with the colonies of Spain and Portugal in South America, the Gulf Coast and Caribbean, shared common characteristics, but also many distinctive differences. England and France were looking to find easily extracted forms of great wealth or great indigenous empires like those of the Aztecs or Inca found in the Latin and South America by the Spanish and Portuguese (Bulliet et al. 2006:396). Distracted by ventures elsewhere, neither England nor France imitated the large and expensive colonial bureaucracies that Spain and Portugal had establish; instead, private companies and individual

proprietors [and merchants] pioneered the development of English and French colonies (Bulliet et al. 2006:396).

Even within North America, colonial development was regionally different. In the south, “colonists pushed deeper into the interior developing a [strong] sustainable economy based on furs, timber, and increasingly tobacco” (Bulliet et al. 2006:396-397). This stable economy attracted new immigrants, bringing with them new sources of capital. Those immigrants who were unable to finance their trip to North America often signed indentures, which contractually obligated them to pay off their debt over a specified period of time in return for travel expenses. During the 17th century, approximately 1500 indentured servants arrived each year, and as a result, Virginia’s slave population grew rapidly from 950 in 1660 to 120,000 by 1756 (Bulliet et al. 2006: 397).

The well-established plantations of the south, in particular, South Carolina, established a hierarchical social order. Rich planters controlled the social, economic, and political arenas, and maintained dual households; For example, one rurally based and the other based in Charleston, SC. Small farmers, cattlemen, artisans, merchants, and fur traders held an intermediate, but clearly subordinate social position, with the slaves occupying the lowest rungs on the social and economic ladder (Bulliet et al. 2006:397).

The New England colonies developed greatly different from the southern colonies. Originally founded by two separate groups, the Pilgrims and the Puritans, Plymouth (founded by the Pilgrims) was eventually integrated into the Massachusetts

Bay Colony of the Puritans after nearly half of the settlement perished during the first winter; by 1643, more than 20,000 Puritans has settled in the Bay Colony (Bulliet et al. 2006:397). While most of the population growth in the south was “unnatural”, due to indentured slavery, whole families tended to settle in the north. “A normal gender balance and a healthy climate resulted in a rapid natural increase in population...[and] was more homogeneous and less hierarchical than the southern colonies (Bulliet et al. 2006:397).

Politically, the northern colonies were more egalitarian then the southern colonies. Northern political institutions were developed out of terms drawn from the royal charter, and consisted of an elected governor along with a council of magistrates drawn from a board of directors, and eventually led to the creation of a lower legislative house that selected its own speaker which began to develop procedures and rules similar to the English House of Commons (Bulliet et al. 2006:397)

Northern colonies were economically different from southern colonies as well. Harsh climate and poor soil quality meant that an economy based in agriculture could only serve to meet basic nutritional requirements. In order to finance the tools, textiles, and other essentials northern colonies needed, they began to provide shipping services to the southern colonies, the Caribbean islands, Africa, and Europe (Bulliet et al. 2006: 397). As opposed to the heavily capitalized monopolies of the southern colonies, and Latin and South America, “New England merchants’ success [developed out of] and rested on market intelligence, flexibility, and streamlined

organization” with Boston leading the way as the largest city in British North America with 16,000 residents (Bulliet et al. 2006:397).

Colonists in all four of the New World colonial empires demonstrated an unsurpassed ability to mix Old World technologies with New World resources and create enormous amounts of wealth through the development and exploitation of the Atlantic System. “The development of the Atlantic system showed Europeans’ [and colonists’] ability to move beyond the conquest and capture of existing systems to create a major new trading system that could transform a region almost beyond belief” (Bulliet et al. 2006:409). Wealth was generated for the metropole, but for the benefit of a much larger merchant class which was able to utilize the gains for substantial reinvestment; in Britain, a high proportion of the reinvestment went into expansion of the merchant marine, its protecting navy, and the ports and industries which served both, and into a series of wars which were fought largely for the defense and expansion of [the] empire (Brookfield 1975:3). In his book, *How Capitalism Saved America: The Untold Story from Pilgrims to the Present*, Thomas DiLorenzo (2004) notes that on the eve of the American Revolution, capitalism had made the American colonists wealthier, taller, and in better health than their British counterparts (p.62, in Vance 2005:83).

King George of Great Britain, tried to forcefully impose British mercantilism on the colonies starting in 1733 with the Molasses Act, followed later by more taxes and restricted trade of the colonies with the Navigation Acts, the Sugar Act, the Stamp Act, the Townsend Acts, and the Tea Act (Vance 2005:83). DiLorenzo (2004)

also brings to light what he considers to be “safeguards” built into the newly written American constitution to protect capitalism: the Contract Clause, the Commerce Clause, the Due Process Clause, the Uniform Taxation Clause, and the General Welfare Clause (Vance 2005:83).

The mid to late 18th century, in particular The American Revolutionary period, saw an end to oppressive foreign control over social, economic and political systems in America. Although the U.S. Constitution created the most democratic government of the era, subjugation was built into the system with only a minority of the adult population being given full rights (Bulliet et al. 2006:464). The newly formed independent country was now ready and able to begin the transition from its mercantile, foreign controlled, economy to the emerging capitalism based form. The mechanism that propelled this transition forward was the industrial revolution.

From 1766 through the 1790's a small group of men, the Lunar Society, met in private meetings in Birmingham, England and laid the framework for the industrial revolution. They developed an ideology oriented toward work and accumulation, emphasizing responsibility to the job and to norms or standards or performance; further, individual and work-group efforts and accomplishments are rewarded, whereas the pre-industrial societies often demanded quite contrary standards because of an other-worldly religious ethic and strong family obligations (Kerr et al. 1960:77-78). “The aggressiveness displayed by the metropolitan manufacturers and exporters lent power to a rising set of voices arguing against the web of mercantilist

restrictions, which were seen as stifling the continued expansion of international trade” (Brookfield 1975:4).

In the 18th century, Britain had the fastest-growing population, food supply, and overseas trade. The population of England and Wales grew from 5.5 million in 1688 to 18 million by 1851 (Bulliet et al. 2006:481). This population explosion and shift from rural to urban based economies coincided with an agricultural revolution to support the needs of the growing masses. The growth of the population and the food supply, in turn, fed trade which “was accompanied by a growing interest in technology and innovation among educated people throughout Europe and eastern North America (Bulliet et al. 2006:482).

Five major innovations in technology sparked the industrial revolution: (1) mass production through the division of labor; (2) new machines and mechanization; (3) a great increase in the supply of iron; (4) the steam engine and the changes it made possible in industry and transportation; and (5) the electric telegraph (Bulliet et al. 2006:484). These innovations further led the influx of the rural populations to the developing urban centers of industry in search of a more stable existence, and the promise of good pay.

In the thirty years it took for the United States to become the world’s leading industrial power (1870-1900), iron and textile production doubled, and the number of workers in manufacturing quadrupled, increasing overall manufacturing output more than 600 percent (Boyer, et al. 2002:353). According to Boyer, et al. (2006), six features dominated the birth of modern industrial America: (1) the exploitation of

immense coal deposits for cheap energy; (2) rapid technological innovation and the spread of the factory system; (3) pressures to compete tooth and nail; (4) the demand for large numbers of new workers; (5) an unprecedented, relentless drop in price levels; (6) and an inadequate money supply that drove interest rates up and restricted credit (p. 353-354).

The late 19th and early 20th centuries saw the development of the industrial revolution in the United States, and paved the way for the capitalist economy to further transform the social, economic, and political lives of Americans. By 1900, an industrial economy dominated by a few mammoth firms had replaced the chaos of early competition among thousands of small companies (Boyer et al. 2002:360). While the Industrial Revolution was forged by the hands of the laborers, the vast majority of them remained marginalized. In spite of the political and economic inequities, social benefits such labor saving products, lower prices for goods, and advances in modes of transportation, manufacturing, communication, allowed for the further concentrating of the populus into what we now call the urban environment¹. Industrialization characteristically redesigns and reshapes its human raw materials, whatever the source; it transforms urban populations of old commercial cities; it transplants peasants farmers, and tribal groups to mines, factories, offices; and it imports labor into empty regions and countries (Kerr et al. 1960:193).

¹ Urban environment will be used to refer to the area contained within the Metropolitan Statistical Area of a city and is synonymous with the terms city, metropolis, as well as community.

An urban environment can be defined as an area with an increased density of human-created structures in comparison to the areas surrounding it; usually featuring a dense population, high degree of industrialization, socialization, and strong economic market system. Between 1870 and 1900, New Orleans's population doubled, Buffalo's tripled, and Chicago's increased more than fivefold; similarly, Philadelphia, New York City, and Chicago each passed the 1-million-person mark and 40% of all Americans lived in cities (Boyer, et al. 2002:374). By the year 2000, there may well be as many as 500 cities worldwide with more than a million inhabitants, while the largest of these, Tokyo, Sao Paulo, Mumbai and possibly Shanghai (though the list is perpetually being revised both upwards and downwards), will perhaps boast populations of more than twenty million trailed by a score of cities, mostly in the so-called developing countries, with upwards of ten million (Harvey 2008). Sometime early next century, if present trends continue, more than half of the world's population will be classified as urban rather than rural (Harvey 2008).

Fueled by the influx of more than 11 million immigrants in search of work, urban growth presented two distinguishing factors: cheap labor for small businesses and industries, and an "unparalleled concentration of resources and markets that dramatically stimulated national economic expansion" (Boyer et al. 2002:374). This unpresided growth was not without its problems. "American workers had always been hostile to competition from immigrants, but industrialization heightened the fear of the newcomer by intensifying that competition" (Yellowitz 1977:128). Immigrant groups volleyed for jobs, power, and influence over the natural born citizens, and the

rapid growth severely strained many of the established urban service sectors including housing, sanitation, and transportation.

Major innovations, particularly in transportation and communication, served to transform the urban environment even further. At the onset of urban development, rich and poor alike lived in close proximity and shared access to resources. The invention of the steam engine, and subsequent development of locomotion, meant that distribution of goods and services was no longer concentrated in the densely packed cities and connected regional metropolises, specialized manufacturing cities, and smaller communities and the surrounding countryside into a vast national urban network (Boyer et al. 2002:375). Further, transportation innovations also precipitated longer and larger commodity flows to and from cities, and in addition, “transport developments adjusted the external relations of cities by emphasizing their relative locational (route) advantages and disadvantages” (Pred 1962:30).

Immigrant groups tended to cluster together in the new urban environments, not merely based on nationality, but with others from their own region or village in the Old World. The presence of extended family social organization is often considered bad for economic growth. “[The extended family] provides shelter and food for all of its members, regardless of their individual contributions, so that the indigent and the indolent alike are cared for in a sort of “social security” system” (Kerr et al. 1960:79). Although they were continuously marginalized, (especially through labor practices, and the conditions they endured in the inner city were often times deplorable) within their tight ethnic bound neighborhoods, “immigrants could

speak their own language, purchase traditional foods, attend Old World [religious] services, and celebrate festivals;" further, "reformers attempts to [control] and change immigrant behavior often heightened the newcomers' sense of ethnic identity" (Boyer et al. 2002:379).

The development of better modes of transportation created a great shift in the urban population distribution and spurred the process of suburban sprawl. "The rich moved to the city's edge, and the poor relocated inward, crowding into abandoned mansions subdivided into apartments" (Boyer et al. 2002:375). In a process referred to as ghettoization, overcrowded "slums" were created when landlords subdivided older buildings into apartments and packed residents in, with income being the deciding factor in the choice and location of housing tenement. The slum and ghetto neighborhoods often bordered industrial districts, forcing the residents to comply with loud noises, pollution, soot from coal furnaces, and other byproducts of the production process. "The tendency to fault the slum dwellers for their own plight characterized even well-intentioned reformers and helped to shape and to distort, middle-class perceptions of the immigrant inner city" (Boyer et al. 2002:380).

By the 1890s, electric street cars or trolleys, had replaced horse drawn carts and cable cars in most of the urban areas. Trolley companies began subsidizing long distance commuting by charging a fixed price per ride rather than by distance; thus, families could move further from the city center without increasing their transportation costs, spurring urban sprawl (Boyer et al. 2002:376). A pattern of informal residential segregation by income through housing standards developed.

“Built for families of a particular income level, certain city neighborhoods and suburbs developed remarkably similar internal standards for lot size and house design. Commuters who rode the new street railways out from the city center could [easily] identify the changing neighborhoods along the way” (Boyer et al. 2002:381).

Although middle and upper-class American residents pushed the outer fringes of the developing urban environment in search of green spaces and fresh air, many of the businesses and professional activities remained in the heart of the city. The growing evidence of social unrest, and the occasional strikes and riots that swept the city, were deeply troubling to these morally conservative classes (Boyer et al. 2002:383). In the 1830s and 1840s cities established police forces to maintain law and order, and “unlike their European counterparts, these regulatory agencies were civilian enterprises, separate from the military and controlled by local officials” which “made little headway in suppressing the rowdy street life, drinking, gambling, and prostitution that flourished in the immigrant working-class districts” (Boyer et al. 2002:382).

Caught between the “immigrant communities resentful of outside meddling” and the “middle-class, rural-based native born citizens who controlled the state legislatures,” the police force made little headway in curtailing urban crime, and often times “in return for payoffs, the police permitted gamblers, prostitutes, and saloon keepers to operate more or less at will in poor neighborhoods where little organized opposition existed, provided they remained discrete” (Boyer et al. 2002:382). Because many of the police officers were drawn from the ranks of the immigrant class and were

sympathetic to the plight of their own kind, the moral urban reformers were unable to legislatively inflict their stricter morality upon the urban lower classes.

The demands placed on public utilities, rapid-transit systems, and fire and police departments forced cities to raise taxes, issue bonds, and create new municipal departments and positions, reflecting the competition for authority and deep seeded power struggle over the urban environment and control of its resources (Boyer et al. 2002:382). Volleying over the revenue streams from these new policies created an even deeper divide between the city governments and state legislatures. Although both claimed jurisdiction over the urban environment, the state legislatures tried to curb governmental abuses by altering city charters, bestowing special contracts and monopolies on railroad and utility magnates, and tried to minimize taxes by reducing the expenses of city government and limiting city services (Boyer et al. 2002:382).

The underlying driving force behind the Industrial Revolution and the development and growth of the urban environment has been the economic theory of capitalism. Capitalism is the socio-economic system that separates the economy from the state (the government does not engage in regulation or control of the market processes, or *laissez-faire*) and places the control over the means of production in the hands of individuals. As stated by Michel Beaud (1983), “capitalism is neither a person nor an institution. It neither wills nor chooses. It is a logic at work through a mode of production: a blind, obstinate logic of accumulation” (p. 115). According to Edwards et al. (1978), there are three distinguishing characteristics of western capitalism: (1) production of goods and services takes the form of commodities that

are produced and sold in the market system rather than being produced for the direct use of the producer; (2) the existence of two distinct classes (capitalists, who maintain a monopoly over the means of production, and wage workers, who sell their capacity to work to the capitalists in exchange for some predetermined wage or salary); and (3) capitalists, not the workers, control the process of commodity production (1978:75-76).

Karl Marx (1820-1895) in *Capital* (1867) defines the commodity in terms of its two distinguishing values: “use value (i.e. those qualities which satisfies some human want), and its exchange value (the proportion in which use values of one kind are exchanged for use values of another kind) expressed in a capitalist economy in the form of money” (Bottomore 1985:6). Commodities are then sold in a competition based market system, which provides the capitalists with surplus value in the form of profit. The accumulation of capital is thereby a central goal of the capitalist economy. Marx and his theories on capitalism will be discussed in greater detail in the next chapter.

Of basic importance to American capitalism is its great emphasis on the rational, acquisitive, individual motivated by self-interests. “‘Individual initiative’- an acquisitive spirit, highly developed, widely diffused - is the mark of a society where labor is a commodity, sold on a more or less competitive market. It is not the “wage system” as such that distinguished western capitalism...it is instead the fact that all labor-salaried or wage-roll, managerial or manual – is formally free to compete for better jobs, better pay, for the best possible place in the economic world” (Wilensky

& Lebeaux 1965:33-34). The means of production become commodities when used by the capitalist to produce surplus value, or the income for the capitalist, in the form of profits by the exploitation of a lower class (Edwards et al. 1987:80-81.)

Capital takes both a material and a social form. Marx points out the inherent class exploitation between the capitalists, or Bourgeoisie, and the working class, or Proletariat. It is not an exaggeration to say that in the early period of economic development coercion has everywhere played the main role in labor recruitment; people have been *pushed* into the factories and the plantations, more than they have been *pulled* by the great opportunity before them (Wilensky & Lebeaux 1965:50). Since the only thing that the property less worker has in the employment relationship is their labor-power, they must relinquish control of that labor (what is produced and how it is produced) in order to facilitate the employment contract; further, the capitalist organize production hierarchically in order to maintain their control over the production process and to further their control over the productivity of their workers. “Consequently, capital is not only part of the forces of production but it is also a particular employment of those forces, a social relation” (Edwards et al. 1987:81). Even social property or objects (in the form of parks, factories, offices, healthcare, social and labor services), is controlled by capitalists. No matter how social in character “private” property may be, the vesting of ownership of society’s economic apparatus in the hands of capitalists gives them the legal right to control that property’s use and distribution (Edwards et. al. 1978:76).

In a *laissez-faire* (hands-off) or free market capitalist system, the government

remains independent of the economic lives of its citizens and relinquishes control over the market system; however it is impossible to remove government involvement so easily from the equation. The bases of economic transactions within the market system are freely formed contracts between individuals. For proper implementation of a capitalist system, a strong political foundation must form the substructure of the government, and that includes the protection, under law, of the binding nature of and enforcement of contracts, recognition and protection of certain rights, in particular the *right to life* and the *right to property*.

As demonstrated, the industrial revolution, and the ensuing economic shift from mercantilism to capitalism, was responsible for the enormous growth of urban America. The growth of manufacturing and other forms of production, along with technological innovations in transportation and communication were responsible for luring millions of new immigrants into the urban environment, as well as persuading many native-born Americans to leave their rural confines in search of prosperity. Although capitalism was the mechanism by which unprecedented economic wealth was accumulated, the underlying contradictions and inherent flaws of this new economic system lay at the root of many of the new problems faced within the urban environment.

The City of Cincinnati, Ohio

The city of Cincinnati lies in the southwestern corner of Ohio, on the Ohio River. Cincinnati began as three settlements between the Little Miami and Great Miami rivers on the north shore of the Ohio River; Columbia was on the Little

Miami; North Bend on the Great Miami; and Losantiville, the central settlement, was opposite the mouth of the Licking River (Cincinnati Museum Center, 2009).

Further, in 1790, Arthur St. Clair, governor of the Northwest Territory, changed the name of the settlement to "Cincinnati" in honor of the Society of the Cincinnati, of which he was president. The Society of Cincinnati (which gets its name from Cincinnatus, the Roman general and dictator, who saved the city of Rome from destruction) honored the ideal of return to civilian life by military officers following the Revolution rather than imposing military rule. This also led to the nickname of "the City of Seven Hills." "The hills form a crescent from the east bank of the Ohio River to the west bank: Mount Adams, Walnut Hills, Mount Auburn, Vine Street Hill, Fairmount, Mount Harrison, and College Hill" (Cincinnati Museum Center, 2009). To this day, Cincinnati is home to a disproportionately large number of descendants of Revolutionary War soldiers.

In 1802, Cincinnati was chartered as a village, and in 1819, it was incorporated as a city. "The introduction of steam navigation on the Ohio River in 1811, and the completion of the Miami and Erie Canal, helped the city grow to 115,000 citizens by 1850" (Cincinnati Museum Center, 2009). Another nickname for Cincinnati, "Porkopolis," was coined around 1835, when Cincinnati was the country's chief hog packing center, and herds of pigs traveled the streets. Cincinnati holds many claims to fame including the first municipal fire department in 1853, the first professional baseball team (the Cincinnati Red Stockings, a.k.a. the Cincinnati Reds) in 1867, the world's first reinforced concrete skyscraper (the Ingalls Building) in

1902, the first to build and own a major railroad in 1880, and the nation's first all electric trading market (the Cincinnati Stock Exchange) in 1976 (Cincinnati Museum Center, 2009). Among with these and many other honors, Cincinnati was also a major stopping point for the Underground Railroad.

Located at the core of the city, Union Terminal played an important part in the development of Cincinnati. According to the Cincinnati Museum Center website, During WWII, Cincinnati Union Terminal experienced unprecedented success. As a major transfer point for soldiers, the station served as many as 20,000 passengers on some days; however, in the 1950s, the sudden expansion of interstates and airlines led to the rapid decline of the railroad industry. Union Terminal was also a stopping point for immigrants moving west.

Cincinnati was chosen for spatial-economic analysis because of its rich history in industrial, communication, transportation, and social development. As with many urban areas developing during this time period, the over crowding of housing, the class and ethnically natured exploitation, the uneven distribution of goods and services, and the concentration of property in the hands of a few created many issues that were unique to the developing urban social, economic, and political structure. The role of capitalism in this process is irrefutable. In the following chapter, capitalism is discussed in further detail. Therein, a theoretical analysis of the role of capitalism in perpetuating urban decay (in terms of housing, income, population, crime, and commodity distribution) is conducted through an integrated approach using classical conflict theory and ecological theories.

CHAPTER 2:

THEORETICAL PERSPECTIVES

In the literature surrounding the study of the dynamics of the urban environment, there are a plethora of theories regarding the nature of development; however, typological approach, classical ecological approach, systems theory, and the conflict theory have emerged as the preeminent points of reference in which to begin studying urban growth and development. Presented in this chapter, is an overview of conflict theory as presented by Karl Marx. His definitions and critique of capitalism as an economic system, provides a framework in which the link between capitalism and urban decay can be examined in terms of various ecological processes. Capitalist ecological development is then explored in terms of the relationship between production and spatial development, and the flaws within these theories. Geographer David Harvey provides an ecological critique of Marx's work and proposes a model including ecologically based methods. This integrated approach can be used to examine the role capitalist market forces play in the perpetuation of urban decay, which can be demonstrated in both spatial and social terms. Spatial and social growth, patterning, and mechanisms will be discussed later in the chapter and defined in depth in the following chapter

Marxian Economics

The need to be productive and the need to be social are distinctive human qualities that capitalism and conflict theory both use to dichotomize the relationship dynamic between humans and their environment. The need to be productive refers to

an individual's ability to direct their actions according to their best judgment, have the ability and freedom to act on those decisions, and to obtain the means necessary to maintain a prolonged existence; this expressed under capitalism as the *right to property*. Social need refers to the individuals desire to belong to a group, or under capitalism, the *right to freely form contracts*; for any social relationship can be reduced to a basic, verbal or written, contract.

Individuals do not have the right to violate another individual's rights. To do this is to exercise unnecessary force unto another. "In a free and just society, no [individual] can claim a moral right to initiate force against another [individual] because it is contrary to the survival requirements for a rational being" (CISC, 2007). It is human nature to be self sufficient, which means that the services or products of one individual can not be demanded by another individual, as this would eliminate the exercise of rationality in the process of pursuing ones own self-interest.

Rationality is vital to this decision making process. Humans must be able to make sense of their surroundings and be able to take what is picked up by their senses and turn it into a conscious decision through deductive reasoning. Whenever reasoning is ignored, for alternative processes such as hope or faith, they lose their ability to control their production and ultimately, the ability to perpetuate their own self-preservation. When coercion, or negative external physical forces are present, humans again lose their ability to control their own production due to the loss of their ability to carry out rational thought processes (CISC, 2007). The application of these negative external forces fundamentally corrupts the underlying social context of

freedom and eliminates individual rights and the ability to make rational decisions.

According to some moral context, individuals make the appropriate choices on how to best direct the course of their life. Along this moral context, most choices usually involve their own self-interests. This builds an “underlying notion of egoism into the basic structure of capitalism” (CISC, 2007).

Capitalism, as an economic system, eliminates the individual’s ability to make rational choices in the procurement of certain materials by limiting their access to certain resources, through spatial distribution of, and economic control of resources, for the benefit of the economic system over the individual. For example, the choice of housing location is dictated by land values and resource utilization more so than personal choice.

As theorized by Karl Marx (1818-1883), the economic system of capitalism, and can be viewed in terms of 4 basic processes: competition, domination, invasion, and succession. He believed that capitalist principles and practices grew out of the fall of feudalism in Europe, and that capitalism really gained momentum as an economic system with the industrial revolutions in Europe, and later the United States. Principle to his argument was the notion that inequality, particularly class inequality, was fundamentally built into the social structure, which consisted of two great antagonistic classes. Capitalism becomes a system utilizing domination as a form of control, by way of exploiting various kinds of contracts which will be discussed in more depth later in this chapter.

One of Marx’s primary foci within capitalism was on structural class

inequality. In the *Communist Manifesto*, Marx, and a later a colleague named Frederick Engels, outlines the methods for examining class structure. They write “In the earlier epochs of history, we find almost everywhere a complicated arrangement of society into various orders, a manifold gradation of social rank” (Marx and Engels 1952, p.419). They go on to say that “society as a whole is more and more splitting up into two great hostile camps, into two great classes directly facing each other: Bourgeoisie and Proletariat” (Marx and Engels 1952, p.419-420). According to Marx, the bourgeoisie (the wealthier portion of individuals who own the means of production), and the proletariats (who are the laborers) are the basic structure of society. He later describes two other classes known as the Petty Bourgeoisie who were small business owners and artisans and the Lumpenproletariat, who were the underclass, and often-unemployed lower ranks.

Central to conflict theory is the subject of property. Marx writes in *The Communist Manifesto* (1872), “The Proletarian is without property; his relation to his wife and children has no longer anything in common with the bourgeois family-relations; modern industrial labour, modern subjection to capital, the same in England as in France, in America as in Germany, has stripped him of every trace of national character” (Tucker, 1978, p. 482). The inability to effectively obtain the resources necessary to meet the basic requirements for a suitable existence creates a economic structure where an individual must turn their labor into a commodity, worth some real value in a highly flawed market system, controlled by a ruling class of citizens. This creates the necessary conditions for domination to take root, leading to a economic,

social, and political centralization of the market systems.

According to Marx, every commodity has two values: the use value and the exchange value. Marx writes, “The utility of a thing makes it a use-value...[and] exchange value...presents itself as a quantitative relation, as the proportion in which values in use of one sort are exchanged for those of another sort, a relation constantly changing with time and place” (1848, p.13). The creation of surplus value is essential to the workings of a capitalist system in that surplus value allows for further acquisition of resources, means of production, and social control. Marx writes that “capitalist production is not merely the production of commodities; it is essentially the production of surplus value...[which is] a specific social relation of production, a relation that has sprung up historically and stamps the labourer as the direct means of creating surplus value” (1848, p.251).

This surplus value is created past the point where an individual’s simple average labor is represented in the commodity being produced. Increasing the surplus value associated with a commodity is the ultimate goal for the capitalist, for it is the surplus value of a commodity, or profit, which keeps the market system moving in a perpetual cycle. Marx notes that commodities are typically exchanged through a process of metamorphosing from a commodity, into money presented against the backdrop of the market system, and eventually back into a commodity, when purchased with money from another individual. The equilibrium that is inherent in this type of exchange is vital for the overall health of the market. Overproduction can essentially hurt the economic system, in that the capitalist notion of supply-and-

demand can ultimately drive prices to rock bottom, and affect the economy as a whole.

It is the basic premise of capitalism to accumulate capital. This can be done by invasion and succession of market systems to increase the viability and utility of a particular commodity. Competition for resources in the market system fuels this growth process. In order for a business to stay competitive in a capitalist economy, they must be constantly making the business bigger and better than the competitor. Competition, under a capitalist economic system, provides a necessary “leveling of the playing field,” in that individuals are supposed to have equal access to resources; however, competition also serves to reduce the exchange relation from that of a social construct, to one that is centered on the “money commodity”, the exploitation of social and labor contracts, and the creation of new immaterial commodities. The Role of money will be discussed later in this chapter. Competition forces in the market system can lead to various problems such as market glut, price fluctuations, misrepresented values, and hoarding.

Central to what Marx called the Law of Capital Accumulation, is the notion that one must continually acquire capital. This process not only affects the owners of the means of production, but simple labor power as well. Accumulation provides capitalists with the physical and ideological means to exploit the labor relation in order to increase surplus value. Physically, the laborer has already been alienated from the products they produce. This alienation provides that capitalist with the opportunity to control the production of commodities so as to perpetuate their own

self-interests. This domination of the physical components leads to a domination of ideologies, which can be just as explicit in their exploitation of human labor power.

Marx believed that the bourgeoisie accumulated capital in order to keep the proletariat oppressed and to stay competitive with other businesses in the system.

Marx writes, "The essential condition for the existence and sway of the bourgeois is the formation and augmentation of capital; the condition for capital is wage labor.

Wage labor rests exclusively on competition between labourers" (1952, p.425). He

continues on saying that "the advance of industry, whose involuntary promoter is the bourgeoisie, replaces the isolation of the labourers, due to competition, by their

revolutionary combination, due to association" (Marx 1952, p.425). The economic

manipulation of the labor contract between worker and employer becomes the mechanism that allows capitalism to direct ecological growth and decay.

For example, Marx mentions the idea of the reserve army of labor. Marx

writes, "the relative mass of the industrial reserve army increases, therefore, with the potential energy of wealth...the greater this reserve army in proportion to the active

labour army, the greater is the mass of a consolidated surplus population, whose

misery is in inverse ratio to its torment of labour" (1848, p.319). Essentially, under a

capitalist system, there is always a surplus of unemployed individuals who are willing

to replace any unruly laborers, and will usually do so for less compensation. This

notion can be useful to the capitalist in several ways. Mainly, they can increase profit

margins and production by exploiting workers based on the working wage

differential. Capitalist can also use the threat of replacement to keep laborers

complacent with the conditions in which they are forced to work, and can keep the machines running. Essentially, capitalists are able to use competition within the ranks of the working classes to manipulate and exploit the labor contract further breaking down solidarity, and to perpetuate their own interests. This is the basis for what Marx called class consciousness.

In reference to the urban environment, Marx writes, “the foundation of every division of labour that is well developed...is the separation between town and country” (Tucker 1978, p.393). Further he writes, “it may be said, that the whole economic history of society is summed up in the movement of this antithesis” (Tucker 1978, p.393). According to conflict theory, the urban environment was the perfect breeding ground for capitalist economics. The high concentration of unskilled workers and growing disdain between ethnically based groups perfectly suited the capitalist needs and provided the reserve army of labor needed to promote their accumulation of capital.

Another conflict theorist, Max Weber (1864-1920), incorporated the basic principles of conflict theory into his argument centered on the use of ideal types in explaining the change of medieval Europe from a feudal society into an individualistic capitalist society. In his works *the Protestant Ethic and the Spirit of Capitalism* (1904), *Economy and Society* (1921), and *Sociology of Religion* (1920-21) he describes his argument on the social, economic, and political transition and through the use of Ferdinand Tönnies notion of the ideal type. As noted by Larry Lyon (1988), “Weber’s distinctions between rational actions based on ‘efficiency’

and the 'amount of return' (*zweckrational*) and the more *Gemeinschaft* actions based on values (*wertrational*), emotion (*affektuell*), or tradition (*traditionell*) are similar to Tönnies original typology" (p.19). Weber's writings also illustrate the way in which social relations of exchange are reduced to a monetary relationship.

Friedrich Engels carried on the notions of Marx, but in a manner that was better suited to the study of the community. Engels published *The Conditions of the Working Class in England in 1844* (1845), which describes the city in terms reminiscent of *Gesellschaft* notions of Ferdinand Tönnies. In reference to the social climate of the city, Engels writes "and they crowd by one another as though they had nothing in common, nothing to do with one another, and their only agreement is the tacit one, that keeps to his own side of the pavement, so as not to delay the opposing streams of the crowd, while it occurs to no man to honour another with so much as a glance" (Engels 1958, in Lyon 1989, p. 66). This alienation, a precondition for the success of capitalism, keeps the urban environment in a constant state of disorder, and reflects Marx's notions of class-consciousness.

Interestingly, Engels points out that while capitalism creates these urban problems, it is unable to curtail them as well. He writes, "as long as the capitalist mode of production continues to exist it is folly to hope for an isolated settlement of the housing question or of any other social question affecting the lot of workers" (Engels 1969, p.75). He concludes that the only way to fix the problems caused by capitalism is to abolish capitalism and its subsequent modes of production. In true Marxist form, the city presents itself in a dialectical fashion. On the one hand, the

social structure is bound together through freely formed contracts, which produce economic gain against a backdrop of a market system; on the other hand, the growth and development of the urban environment is dependent on the ecological boundary of its primary and secondary market systems.

In order to sustain its market system substructure, capitalism utilizes a series of ecological qualities, and develops a way to exploit the contract between labor and environmental resources, giving capitalism control over growth mechanisms. The commodification of ecological space presents a scenario where the ecological boundaries of a given market system become dependent on the subsequent market system's waves of growth and decline, supply and demand. Thus, urban decay becomes a consequence of market particularities, disproportionate resource distribution, and exploited ecological contracts.

The Ecological Approach

The ecological approach to studying the community is subdivided into four main areas of analysis: classical, socio-cultural, neo-orthodox, and SSA/factorial analysis. The classical ecological approach to studying the community developed out of the University of Chicago, referred to as the Chicago School, by the chair of the sociology department Robert E. Park, and his colleagues Ernest W. Burgess and Roderick D. McKenzie.

Park, along with his colleagues, saw the urban center as a social organism, which operated much as a physical organism does in nature, with their theory centering on the interplay of individuals and their environment. In *The City* (1925)

Park writes, “The city is not...merely a physical mechanism and an artificial construction; it is involved in the vital processes of the people who construct it... [and] it is a product of nature, and particularly of human nature” (1925:1). Further, Park writes, “we may...think of the city, that is to say, the place and the people, with all the machinery and administrative devices that go with them, as organically related; a kind of psychophysical mechanism in and through which private and political interests find not merely a collective, but a corporate expression” (1925:2).

Robert Park coined the term “Human Ecology” as a way to apply biological processes to the development of urban areas. Taking a positivistic approach, they borrowed the four main characteristics of biological ecology and applied them to the urban environment: competition, invasion, succession, and domination. R. D. McKenzie (1925) defines human ecology as the “study of the spatial and temporal relations of human beings as affected by the selective, distributive, and accommodative forces of the environment” (p. 64). Further, “human ecology is fundamentally interested in the effect of *position* (place relation of a given community), in both time and space, upon human institutions and human behavior” (McKenzie 1925:64). They saw adaptation to environmental changes essential to the survival of both the social and organic worlds, and built his model of urban growth with this underlying premise.

As in biology, Park et al. saw that the development and maintenance of human communities was directly related to the food supply, and of the “role played in the wider ecological process of production and distribution of commodities” (McKenzie

1925:65). In terms of human settlement patterns, McKenzie notes:

“When man makes his living from hunting or fishing, the community is small and of but temporary duration; when agriculture becomes the chief source of sustenance, the community is still small but assumes a more permanent character; when trade and commerce develop, larger communities arise at points of break in conveyance, that is, at the mouths of rivers, junctions of streams, at waterfalls, and shallows where streams are forded; as new forms of transportation arise, new points of concentration occur and old points become accentuated or reduced” (1925:65-66).

Ecologically speaking, communities can be divided into four general types:

First, the *primary service community*, (such as the agricultural town, the fishing, mining, or lumbering community) serves as the first step in the distributive process of the outgoing basic commodity and as the last stage in the distributive process of the product finished from consumption (McKenzie 1925:66). The size of the community depends entirely on the nature of the extractive industry supporting it, along with the viability of its trade routes, and is typically contains no more than a few thousand residents.

The second type of community is the *commercial community*. This type of community fulfils the secondary functions in the distributive process of commodities, collecting the basic materials from the surrounding primary communities and distributing them in the wider markets of the world, as well as redistributing the products coming from other parts of the world to the primary service communities for final consumption (McKenzie 1925:66-67). The size of this type of community is dependent upon its distributive functions, varying from “a small wholesale town in the center of an agricultural plain to that of a great port city whose hinterland extends

halfway across the continent... with growth dependent on the comparative advantages of the site location” (McKenzie 1925:67).

The third type of community that McKenzie describes is the *industrial town*. This type of community serves as the locus for the manufacturing of commodities, and may combine the functions of the primary service and the commercial types; it is also characterized by the relative dominance of industry over the other forms of service (McKenzie 1925:67). There is practically no limit to the size to which this type of community can grow; however, “growth is dependant on the scope of and market organization of the particular industries which happen to be located within its boundaries” (McKenzie 1925:67). Within this type of community, there are two further general type distinctions: (1) those that have diversified and multiple industries organized on a local sale of products; and (2) those that are dominated by one or two highly developed industries organized on a national or world-sale or products (McKenzie 1925:67).

The fourth type of community is one, which is lacking in a specific economic base. “It draws its economic sustenance from other parts of the world, and may serve no function in the production or distribution of commodities (McKenzie 1925:67). The growth (or decline) of these types of communities, according to McKenzie, “are not subject to the same laws that govern the development of towns that play a part in the larger productive and distributive processes” (McKenzie 1925:67).

Park describes the nature of the “artificial construction” behind the spatial layout of most American cities as a checkerboard, with the block as the basic unit of

distance. He goes on to point out that, “under our system of individual ownership...it is not possible to determine in advance the extent to concentration of population which is likely to occur in any given area...[for] the city cannot fix land values, and we leave to private enterprise, for the most part, the task of determining the city’s limits and the location of its residential and industrial districts” (Park 1925:4).

Ernest Burgess presents a model of urban growth termed *The Concentric Zone Model*. The Concentric Zone model can be described as an expansion of population away from a central point, utilizing the basic four components of the urban ecological model. According to Burgess, “The typical process of the expansion of the city can be illustrated, perhaps, by a series of concentric circles, which may be numbered to designate both the successive zones of urban extension and the types of areas differentiated in the process of expansion” (1925:50) There are five zones that developed within the Concentric Zone model.

Burgess describes the Concentric Zone Model and the five zones as follows:

“This [model] represents an ideal construction of the tendencies of any town or city to expand radially from its central business district... ‘The Loop’ (I). Encircling the downtown area there is normally an area of transition, which is being invaded by business and light manufacture (II). A third area (III) is inhabited by the workers of industries who have escaped from the area of determination (II) but who desire to live within the easy access of their work. Beyond this zone is the “residential area” (IV) of high-class apartment buildings or of exclusive “restricted” districts of single family dwellings. Still further out beyond the city limits, is the Commuters’ Zone (V)- suburban areas, or satellite cities- within a thirty-to sixty- minute ride of the central business district” (1925:50).

This model demonstrates two of the four components of ecological theory, invasion

and succession. Burgess writes, “[it is the] tendency of each inner zone to extend its area by the *invasion* of the next outer zone; this aspect of expansion may be called *succession*...” (1925:50).

Along with invasion and succession, the process of urban expansion involves domination of resources through the processes of centralization and decentralization. Burgess explains centralization as, “in all cities there is a natural tendency for local and outside transportation to converge in the central business district...[which is where] we expect to find the department stores, the skyscraper office buildings, the railroad stations, the great hotels, the theaters, the art museum, and the city hall; almost inevitably, the economic, cultural, and political life centers here” (1925:52). Further, in terms of decentralization, Burgess notes “...recently sub-business centers have grown up in outlying zones. These “satellite loops” do not, it seems, represent the “hoped for” revival of the neighborhood, but rather a telescoping of several local communities into a larger economic entity, and fueling competition for fewer and fewer resources” (1925:52).

Succession causes the central business district (Zone I) to become rundown and undesirable for habitation, except for those who cannot afford to live anywhere else, for whatever means. According to this model, through the process of neighborhood succession and competition for resources, the inner city becomes an area overrun with crime and deviance. According to Burgess:

“An essential element in the mores and in personal morality is consistency, consistency of the type that is natural in the social control of the primary group. Where mobility is the greatest and where in

consequence, primary controls break down completely, and in the zone of deterioration in the modern city, there develops areas of demoralization, of promiscuity, and of vice" (1925:59).

As pointed out by Burgess, the heterogeneity of the population, and the lack of effective social controls in these areas, lead to the decentralization of authority and resources; pushing them further out of the city, leaving the core alienated and isolated from the rest of the city.

This model spread rapidly during the post war era, but was soon refuted by contemporary theorists. Burgess' model was seen as faulty and was later simplified in "its conception of the suburban commuter fringe, at first to a contrast between industrial and residential suburbs and then to the singular myth of the middle-class enclave (Harris & Lewis, 1998)." "The zonal model was consistent with the idea that social variability could be reduced to a few generalizations (i.e., laws). In its binary (city-suburb) or more continuous (gradient) form, it was suited both to statistical testing and also to the application of parsimonious mathematical models (Harris & Lewis, 1998)." Hughes (1972) points out the inherent deficiencies in the concentric zone model. He writes, "Although Park contended that society formed a superstructure lying above the competitive biotic community, he never clearly established the relationship of societal forces to community structure" (1972:35).

Homer Hoyt was the Principal Housing Economist for the Federal Housing Administration at the time he proposed his theory of sector specialization, or sector theory (1939). Sector Theory, as built off of the Concentric Zone Model, suggests that

zones expand outward from the city center along railroads, highways, and other transportation arteries in a wedge shaped pattern. In his study of 142 American cities, Hoyt noticed that instead of a random mixture of residential home values and rents in small or cities of small growth, higher income families lived in one or more wedges shaped sectors of the city, typically opposite the manufacturing sectors (Hoyt 1965:586). Hoyt also noted that “the growth of such areas tends to proceed along established lines of travel; along the fastest existing transportation lines; toward higher ground; toward the homes of community leaders; in the direction of free, open country and in the same general direction as the trend of movement of the chief retail and office buildings” (1939:588).

James W. Hughes (1972) in *Urban Indicators, Metropolitan Evolution, and Public Policy*, summarizes the three main tendencies Hoyt discovered:

1. The various groups in the social order tend to be segregated into rather definite areas according to their income or social positions.
2. The highest income groups live in the houses, which command the highest prices and rents, while the lower-income groups live in houses, which are offered for the lower prices and rents. Generally the low rent areas are located first near the business and industrial center of the city and then tend to expand outward on one side or sector of the city which is not pre-empted by higher rent residential areas or by business and industrial districts.
3. The principle growth of American cities has taken place by new building at the periphery rather than by the rebuilding of older areas. This means that some of our cities are beginning to resemble a ‘hollow shell’ with the major demands for land uses by-passing many of the ‘near-in’ areas. In other cases these near-in areas become slums with little possibility of being rehabilitated through ordinary market processes. (p.36).

Hoyt faulted the classical concentric zone model for being too simplistic in nature. He

states that if the concentric zone theory of the location of rent areas be accepted literally, then the high rent areas would encompass the entire outer periphery of the city, and his analysis of 142 cities demonstrates that high rent areas and low rent areas develop according to the lines of transportation and manufacturing instead of successive zones (Hoyt 1965:586). Hoyt also added a directional component to spatial patterning. Further, sector theory maintains, "that the urban growth process is represented by a distinct axial pattern of sectors; new and future growth occurs at the outer rim of each sector, tending to sustain the sector's present character" (Hughes 1972:37).

The multiple nuclei model is an ecological model put forth by Chauncy (C.D.) Harris and Edward Ullman in the 1945 article *The Nature of Cities*. Central to this model is the lack of a defined CBD, like other previous ecological models had emphasised. They argue that while a city may have started with a CBD, similar industries with common land-use and financial requirements are established near each other, and advancements in transportation lead to the development of "minicenters" within the larger urban metropolitan context (Harris & Ullman 1945:230). Hughes (1972) points out that the number of nuclei is a function of both locational forces and of historical development (p.37).

Harris and Ullman note that the initial nucleus is typically located in retail districts, near port or rail facilities, or the factory, mine or beach in others. The rise of separate nuclei and differentiated districts reflects a combination of four factors:

1. Certain activities require specialized facilities. For example, the retail

district is attached to the point of greatest intracity accessibility, the port district to suitable water front, manufacturing districts to large blocks of land and water or rail connection, etc.

2. Certain like activities group together because they profit from cohesion. Retail districts benefit from grouping which increases the concentration of potential customers and makes comparison shopping possible.
3. Certain unlike activities are detrimental to each other. For example, the antagonism between manufacturing districts and high-class residential development.
4. Certain activities are unable to afford the high rents of the most desirable sites. For example, low-class housing unable to afford the luxury of high land with a view. (Harris & Ullman 1945:229-230).

The larger and more specialized a city is, the more nuclei it tends to have. Similar to concentric zone and sector theories, Harris and Ullman then generalize that most American cities have districts that have developed around nuclei, including the CBD, wholesale and light manufacture, heavy industry, residential, suburbs and satellites, and minor nuclei which includes parks, cultural centers, and small industrial applications (1945:231-232).

Similar to Hoyt's Sector Theory, Harris and Ullman noted that housing of different types and values developed along communication avenues, and that topography also played a role in determining the value of the housing constructed i.e. higher topography usually meant higher land and home value. Finally, they noted that particular types of development directly affected the value of adjacent land, paving the way for commercialized, industrialized, and residential pockets to form, eliminating the need for a CBD altogether (Harris & Ullman 1945:232).

In terms of concentric zone and sector theories, Harris and Ullman state that "both [of these theories] emphasize the general tendency of central residential areas to

decline in value as new construction takes place on the outer edges; the sector theory is, however, more discriminating in its analysis of that movement (1945:232). Still, Harris and Ullman's multiple nuclei theory shares with Hoyt's sector theory, and Burgess' concentric zone theory the proposition that urban structure and growth is not random; rather it is systematic and predictable (Lyon 1998, p. 39).

An article published in 1945 by Walter Fiery entitled *Sentiment and Symbolism as Ecological Variables*, criticises the classical ecological approach to studying community and takes a sociocultural ecological stance. In a study conducted in Boston, Fiery (1945) was able to show "It is the symbolic quality of [Beacon Hill], not its impeditive or cost-imposing character, that most tangibly correlates with the retentive, attractive, and resistive trends that we have observed" and "it is the dynamic force of spatially referred sentiments, rather than considerations of rent, which explains why certain families have chosen to live on Beacon Hill in preference to other in-town districts having equally accessible location and even superior housing conditions" (Fiery 1945:238). Further Larry Lyon (1998) notes that "such events as the refusal of Beacon Hill's residents to sell homes in their traditional high-status neighborhood to commercial interests and the retention of the Boston Commons Park in the middle of the CBD could be explained only through reference to sentiment and symbolism" (p.39). Classical ecology models are also commonly refuted to be tainted with ecological fallacies, or the use of ecological correlations to explain patterns in individual behaviors.

Socio-cultural ecology aimed to incorporate culture and values into ecological assumptions. Fiery's study of Boston did so by focusing on the cultural significance associated with Beacon Hill and the Boston Commons Park, and the values attached to these community features by its residents. To further emphasize this critique of classical ecological models, Lyon (1998) mentions that August Heckscher (1977) argued "that the spacial patterns of American cities clearly reflect American values of freedom, individualism, growth, and business success" citing how "the American grid pattern of streets allows people to look down the entire street, even out to the countryside and envision urban expansion" (Lyon 1998, p.40).

Due to their emphasis on cultural variables, sociocultural ecologists are often times hard to distinguish from the general mainstream sociological literature. Symbolic interactionism grew out of the sociocultural ecology approach and remains as the last discriminating evidence of this particular approach to the study of the community. Lyon (1998) notes how works by Strauss (1961), Suttle (1972), and Hunter (1973) develop the symbolic interactionist perspective on sociocultural ecology and studies of the community through their use of imagery, cultural values, and symbolism and their relationship to the ecological structure and development, criticizes this approach for its inability to become an independent faction of social ecology and developing a unique and distinctive blend of cultural and ecological attributes (1998, p.41-42).

Amos Hawley and his subsequent publication of *Human Ecology: A Theory of Community Structure* (1950) was able to once again establish the ecological approach

as significant to the study of community through neo-orthodox ecology. Hawley was able to do what the sociocultural ecologists could not accomplish; creating a distinctive ecological approach from classical roots. He did so by “moving the focus of the approach away from spatial distributions (which he felt was more a geographical perspective rather than an ecological one) and on to the adaptation of human populations by means of structural differentiation” (Lyon 1998, p. 42). Hawley dismissed Park’s original view of the biotic v. the cultural and developed the notion of adaptive mechanisms such as technology and social organizations as a means of creating a measure of ecological principles. His use of these adaptive mechanisms once again placed the community back in the realm of study as a unit of analysis.

Following Hawley’s neo-orthodox approach, Otis Dudley Duncan created “his “ecological complex” of four basic, interrelated, reference variables: population, organization, environment, and technology; or POET for short” (Lyon, 1998, p.43). This framework includes “standard population measures (size, heterogeneity), organizational types (developed as adaptation for survival), environmental phenomena (including all variables external to the community), and technological developments (skills or tools to aid adaptation); ...and the POET framework ensures that important ecological variable can be studied across a wide array of various principles“ (Lyon 1998, p. 43). By utilizing this framework, statistical measures and safeguards can be used as an effective and accurate tool for measuring the community.

Furthering the quantitative emphasis on community analysis, Social Area Analysis, or SAA, and factorial ecology draw upon classical ecological principles as well as quantitative data to support ecological community analysis. While natural areas are the building blocks of classical ecology, census tracts developed as the preferred unit of measure for SAA. In 1940, the US Census Bureau began to publish its data for most cities according to census tracts. Cities can often times have hundreds of census tracts, which can present an overwhelming task for social scientists when trying to compile census data. Lyon (1998) points out that “for the first time urban ecologists were faced with more statistical data than they could assimilate and SAA was developed in order to group similar census tracts into larger categories that fulfilled the same functions as the earlier [classical ecological] concept of natural areas” (1998, p. 44). There are seven primary variables, further broken down into three indexes: social status (measured by occupational prestige and education), family status (measured by fertility ratio, number of women in the labor force, and number of single family dwellings), and ethnic status (measured by percent foreign born or black).

Criticisms for SAA abound, primarily in the lack of a theoretical framework and the emphasis on an oversimplified set of only seven social variables. Bell (1955) used the statistical procedure of factor analysis to validate the primary seven variables of SAA. “Factor analysis identifies clusters of related variables (factors) by analyzing the variables, identifying their underlying similarities, and summarizing them on a single index score (or factor score)” (Lyon 1998, p. 44-45). This statistical

analysis provides a comparison of similar census tracts based on the seven variables, as well as, cities with similar data set. While this could be useful in the study of communities, as with neoclassical ecology, there is an over emphasis on aggregated data which can lead to ecological fallacies and skewed results.

In light of the debate over the use of SAA and factorial ecology, three important findings have evolved from this paradigm. First, approximately five factors underly the ecological structure of American communities which includes, socioeconomic status or SES, family status, ethnicity, resident mobility, and population and functional size. Second, these patterns are distributed systematically. Thirdly, industrialization appears to account for much of the substructure of communities (Lyon 1998, p.46-47).

Although these approaches provide an adequate framework in which to study urban community development on their own, one must take both sides of the argument into account and construct a framework for analysis that integrates both the ecological and conflict perspectives in order to fully understand the dialectical nature of the relationship between the urban environment and its inhabitants, and the mechanisms that binds together. Capitalism is one such mechanism. Using an integrated approach to studying the effects of capitalism on the decay of the urban environment allows sociologists to consider the concepts independently, while also providing a lens in which to analyze the dialectical nature of the relationship.

The Role of Capitalism in Urban Decay

English geographer David Harvey and his works *Limits to Capital* (1982) and

Urbanization of Capital (1985), provides a uniquely distinctive neo-Marxian approach to studying the community. Harvey believes that the spatial patterns of city development are consistent with the underlying capitalist economic system. "These spatial patterns are dynamic because the dialectical contradictions of capitalism require constant adjustments to maintain the system" (Lyon 1998, p. 75).

Harvey contends that in order to maintain their profit margins, capitalists purposefully overproduce commodities, leading to glutted markets, drastic negative price shifts, and rises in unemployment. These markets can be temporarily curtailed through a redirection of investments from primary circuits (production) to secondary circuits (warehousing, offices), which allows the capitalist to alter the urban environment through expansion and construction, eventually, causing an increase in production. "The recurring problems of market glut are now exacerbated by the demolition of structurally sound buildings for new largely vacant, blocks of offices (Lyon 1998, p. 76). Brownfield areas are a result of this market glut.

Brownfield areas are abandoned or underused industrial and commercial facilities created as these facilities relocate to the other areas of the city. The resulting vacant land may be contaminated by low concentrations of hazardous waste or pollution, or socially perceived as environmentally contaminated. Brownfield areas do have the potential to be reused once it is physically or socially decontaminated. This process is responsible for creating the conditions that perpetuate urban decay and the subsequent growth and development of the suburban regions of a city.

In true neo-Marxian form, Harvey's analysis is better suited for providing an

integrated approach to the examination of the inherent social, economic, and political injustices of capitalism and its role in urban development, by including the ecological component to the principles of conflict theory. Harvey writes, “A genuinely humanizing urbanism has yet to be brought into being. It remains for revolutionary theory to chart the path from an urbanism based on exploitation to an urbanism appropriate for the human species” (Harvey 1973, p. 314). Harvey notes that Marx was too focused on the means of production and only skimmed the surface when it came to the ecological side of the argument. Marx touches on land rent and value in Volume 3 of Capital, but only so far as to consider the human productivity objectified in the commodities produced from the land.

Harvey argues that Marx stops short of an adequate explanation by contending that the spatial distribution of resources within an urban environment is directly related to capitalist market forces. The post World War I and the Great Depression era saw a huge influx of immigrants into American Cities. The industrial revolution in America was a golden ticket to immigrants seeking opportunity and the promise of steady work. The resulting urbanism and urbanization processes produced radical changes in the social, economic, and political climates of these centers. The following section will demonstrate how capitalism, through very specific ecologically based processes, coordinates and perpetuates the material exploitation and social disintegration of urban decay.

Material Exploitation

The driving force behind capitalism is the production, distribution, and exploitation of commodities against the backdrop of a market system, through ecologically based processes (competition, invasion, domination, succession). Harvey argues that land takes on value separate from the objectified human labor that Marx argues. He states that under conditions of commodity production, production and consumption are separate by exchange, but the appropriation of nature remains fundamental in that we can never ignore what Marx calls 'the material side' of commodities; to do so would be to remove the satisfaction of human wants and needs from any relation to nature (Harvey 1982:5).

According to Harvey, Marx recognizes that private persons can, under the laws of private property, acquire monopoly over definite portions of the globe, as exclusive spheres of their private will to the exclusion of all others (Marx, in Harvey 1982:334). Further, since the land is monopolizable and alienable, it can be commodified and rented or sold in the market, and the hallmark of landed property under capitalism is the total separation of the land as an instrument of production from landed property and the landowner (Harvey 1982:335). The ecological components of land (i.e. waterfalls, fertile soil, trees) represent the natural value. Even though there may be no human labor power objectified in the land, manufacturers stand to receive excess profits in perpetuity by virtue of the natural advantages they enjoy. Further, landowners can appropriate these excess profits and

convert them to into ground-rents without in any way diminishing the average profit (Harvey 1982:336).

According to Harvey (1982) rent is that theoretical concept through which political economy traditionally confronts the problem of spatial organization...and provides a basis for various form of social control over the spatial organization and development of capitalism (p.337). According to Marx, this control can be so because land serves not only as a means of production, but also as a 'foundation, as a place and space providing a basis of operations'- space is required as an element of *all* production and human activity (Marx in Harvey 1982:337). Harvey contends that Marx basically left that as his argument; he solely looked at land from a material commodity frame of reference. Harvey states that since space is used by everyone- not just producers- we have to consider the implications of 'more favored' locations from the standpoint of all forms of human activity, including those of consumption (Harvey 1982:339).

Harvey writes that the cost of reproduction, and therefore the value of labor power, is sensitive to the cost of getting to and from work. Harvey writes, "If all workers receive a flat rate, then those who live in 'favored conditions' have a relative advantage over those who live further away. If the wage is set at a level needed to ensure the reproduction of the worker who lives the farthest away...then all other workers receive a wage somewhat above value. It then follows that those who hold land can convert the excess wage into ground-rent without in any way disturbing the value of labor power" (1982:340).

Marx and Harvey both point out that the appropriation of rents based on location becomes complex and cumbersome when relative 'natural' advantages are taken into account because they are perpetually altering with respect to particular land parcels. "They alter historically, according to economic development, ...the instillation of means of communication, the building of towns, etc., and the growth of population" (Marx, in Harvey 1982:340). Further, the "changing capacity of the transport industry is particularly important since the relative differences may be shifted about...in a way that does not correspond to the geographical distances. The net effect in some cases, may be to even out differences arising from location, but in others exactly the opposite result can be achieved" (Marx, in Harvey 1982:340).

Harvey follows by saying that the key point is that "the locational advantages for specific land parcels can be altered by human agency... which means that the action of capital itself (particularly through investment in transport and communications) can create spatial relationships" (Harvey 1982:341). "The spatial attributes of use values can then be brought back into the realm of analysis as socially created qualities and, therefore, as a fit and proper subject for full investigation in relation to the operation of the law of value" (Harvey 1982:341).

Difficulties in spatial analysis arise when investment of capital practices are considered for the investment of capital modifies both spatial relations and the qualities of land at particular sites. Harvey writes that "money can be put to improving transportation and so opening up more fertile lands for exploitation, or it can be put to improving the inferior lands already in cultivation; the former strategy,

because of the relativity of space, will likely benefit many land owners, whereas the latter is more exclusively confined to individual owners” (1982:342). Marx bypasses these difficulties by concentrating his analysis on differentials in fertility in relation to agricultural production. Marx justifies this simplification in that “the price of production for agricultural commodities is usually fixed by the cost of production on the worst soil plus the average rate of profit” (Harvey 1982:342).

Typically, price in industrial operations is set according to the prevailing social average. Marx’s departure from this process can be justified on two grounds. “First, ‘naturally based’ differentials in productivity cannot be eliminated by technological change in the same way as industry (excess profits are a permanent fixture for those blessed with more fertile soils). Secondly, an expansion in agricultural production entails drawing more inferior lands into cultivation and intensifying production on superior soils only when that is more profitable” (Harvey 1982:342). Further, Harvey contends that whichever the case, the worst soil must always realize the average rate of profit if it is to stay in cultivation or production (1982:342).

This brings to light the problems faced by the rural peasantry during the beginning of the industrial revolution. “The massive exploitation of a rural peasantry by a landlord class is, from this standpoint, entirely consistent with industrial capitalist when it provides cheap food for the urban workers and a cheap supply of raw materials for industry. A powerful alliance can be created between the landed interests and an industrial bourgeoisie on this basis” (Harvey 1982:345). This

exploitation was translated into unparalleled urban expansion, both in economic market substructures and in spatial expansion.

Spatial development takes on capitalistic qualities through the transformation of it into an alienable commodity. The economic sub-market for land becomes subject to market fluctuation just like any other commodity. It is through the buying and selling/renting of land that creates the conditions for spatial expansion and contraction of urban environments. Harvey notes that land becomes a form of fictitious capital, and the land market functions simply as a particular branch of the circulation of interest bearing capital. (1982:347). Further, under such conditions, the land is treated as a pure financial asset which is bought and sold according to the rent it yields...and like all such forms of fictitious capital, what is traded is a claim upon future revenues, which means a claim on future profits from the use of the land or, more directly, a claim upon future labor (Harvey 1982:347). Harvey argues “when land is reduced to a special branch of the circulation of interest-bearing revenue, landownership has achieved its true capitalistic form” (1982:347).

The capitalist form of private property would not have come about without specific conditions. Harvey points out that the growth of commodity exchange, the spread of monetary relationships, and the growth of the credit system all form contextual conditions favorable to the increasing treatment of land as a financial asset (1982:348).

Marx did not undertake any analysis of land markets for he felt that the theoretical underpinnings he used to construct his ground-rent theory were of greater

importance. Harvey notes that “the theory of ground-rent resolves the problem of how land, which is not a product of human labor, can have a price and exchange as a commodity” (1982:367). He point out that “ground-rent, capitalized as the interest on some imaginary capital, constitutes the ‘value’ of the land...and what is bought and sold is not the land, but title to the ground-rent yielded by it” (Harvey 1982:367). The title to the land, in fact, becomes fictitious capital.

Landowners and market forces thereby play an intricate and important role in the ecological development of an urban environment. “The land market shapes the allocation of capital to land and thereby shapes the geographical structure of production, exchange and consumption, the technical division of labor in space, the socioeconomic spaces of reproduction, and so forth” and “the land market is a powerful force making for the rationalization of geographical structures in relation to competition” (Harvey 1982:369).

As mentioned in the previous chapter, advancements in technology, and in particular transportation, played a vital role in urban growth patterns. “The stimulus to revolutionize these arises out of the need to diminish the circulation time of commodities, to extend markets geographically and so simultaneously to build the possibility for cheapening raw material inputs, expanding the basis for realization while accelerating the turnover time of capital” (Harvey 1982:369). This means that if rent is dependent on location, and the relative location stands to be transformed by improved transportation, then transportation investments stand to increase land values in close proximity (Harvey 1982:369). Harvey views location “as a fundamental

material attribute of human activity but recognizes that location is socially produced” (1982:374).

Marx’s principles of the accumulation of wealth are the driving force behind the economic, political, and social decline of the urban environment. Factories, searching for ways to increase profit margins move to areas where land rents are cheaper, they have easy access to modes of transportation, and an available workforce, while simultaneously lowering the employee’s rate of pay, amount of insurance coverage, and the investment ratio paid into employee retirement accounts.

As these companies push the outer expanses of the city limits, a “void” is created where the hustle and bustle of the city used to be. This void is characterized by a lack of jobs, lack of adequate affordable housing, and the inability to obtain the resources that are needed to sustain a quality of life that is deemed acceptable by the majority of society’s standards. As more and more people start pushing the outer expanses of the city, there are a greater number of disadvantaged people left behind in the inner city, further increasing class and economic stratification. In his 1985 work, *Urbanization of Capital*, David Henry presents an argument centering on the accumulation and circulation of capital, pointing out the urban environment is built, destroyed, and rebuilt in order to allow for the efficient circulation of capital (Henry, 1985). Gentrification of the inner city has become popular trend in recent years, but this only serves to make the situation worse. New luxury high rise condos replace dilapidated buildings and commercial centers, but are financially out of the reach of the population living in the inner city that have just lost their homes to these

ambitious projects.

Another problem faced by growing urban centers is the shift to the outsourcing jobs. The Marxist principle of the Labor Theory of Value perfectly explains the motivation behind this practice. Millions of American jobs are being shipped to other countries due to the fact that lower wages can be paid for performing the same services. According to Cyber Futuristics, 2 million jobs will move from the United States and Europe to cheaper destinations in the financial services business alone. The emigration of service jobs across all industries could be as high as 4 million (Cyfuture.com, 2008). They also point out that 3/4 of major financial institutions and investment banks will allocate tasks to low labor cost countries (with India at the top of the list), and that Global financial institutions are predicted to invest \$356 billion in India for outsourcing projects (Cyfuture.com, 2008). As many as 3.3 million U.S. jobs and \$136 billion in wages could be moved to such countries as India, China, and Russia by 2015 (Cyfuture.com, 2008).

Capitalist markets are subject to a cyclical nature; there are periods of growth, and decline, or supply and demand. If the actual value of a commodity were used against the backdrop of a market system, the high degree of variability for commodities would create substantial problems for the economic system. Because of this inconsistency, money takes a powerful position within the framework of capitalism, acting as the universal equivalent. Money, under a capitalist economic system, is a commodity chosen to represent exchange, and as a store of value for a contract that has been made. In a free capitalist economy, governmental control of

money is absent, preserving individual rights, but that is very often not the case.

Money is what makes the division of labor economically possible in that it represents a set value that is not possible under a bartering or trade based economy. Since there is a fixed productive value to this commodity, it makes possible the ability to exchange it for other commodities. Money becomes a symbol of productivity when the exchange value of the commodity is recognized as fixed, by producers in an economy, thus storing its productive value. "To the extent that the government protects individual rights, especially the right to property in every commodity including money, an economy can benefit from the increased productivity and wealth that a stable medium of exchange can provide" (CISC, 2007).

The banking industry has been around since before the concept of capitalism. "Banks facilitate and foster economic activity...but only perform their vital functions fully and best under a system of individual rights and capitalism" (CISC, 2007).

Banks take advantage of the right to contracts in order to facilitate their financial activities. Deposit receipts acted in lieu of actual currency, since the currency was held in trust at the banking institution. "Since the receipts-which in legal form were a contract for storage and disbursement of gold-could be taken to the warehouse and exchanged for gold, they served as a convenient circulating currency" (CISC, 2007).

There is a certain amount of risk involved in the banking industry. As CISC points out, "In return for the risk incurred by the depositor as well and the inconvenience of not having immediate access to his gold on demand, the gold on deposit would earn interest. Banking thus served a specialized role in a division of

labor economy” (CISC, 2007). This role served as a third party mediator between the “productive individuals with large capital reserves [who] might wish to lend some of their money at interest, and the entrepreneurial individuals with new ideas [who] might require borrowing capital to start their businesses” (CISC, 2007). Under a capitalist economic system, banks must compete for customers just like every other individual involved in the market system. They are just as vulnerable to the supply and demands of the market, and must be adaptive in the products they offer to their potential clients.

The economic system of credit is a duel edged sword stuck in the back of the global market system. On one hand, credit allows individuals to purchase the materials the need to sustain their existence when they may not have the available funds to do so; on the other, the credit system has allowed individuals to live outside their means, further complicating the market system as a whole. According to creditcards.com, there were 984 million bank-issued Visa and MasterCard credit card and debit card accounts in the U.S in 2006 (Creditcards.com, 2008) This website also points out that on average, today's consumer has a total of 13 credit obligations on record at a credit bureau. These include credit cards (such as department store charge cards, gas cards, and bank cards) and installment loans (auto loans, mortgage loans, student loans, etc.). Not included are savings and checking accounts (typically not reported to a credit bureau). Of these 13 credit obligations, nine are likely to be credit cards and four are likely to be installment loans (Creditcards.com, 2008). According to the Federal Reserve, the total U.S. consumer debt (which includes credit card debt

and non-credit-card debt, but not mortgage debt) reached \$2.55 trillion at the end of 2007, up from \$2.42 trillion at the end of 2006 (Creditcards.com, 2008).

The universality of the money commodity and the rise of the credit system have presented society with a rather difficult conundrum. On one hand, credit allows individuals access to resources they may not otherwise have access too. On the other hand, the credit system is one of the primary factors in the recent economic trouble of the United States. Individual abuses of the credit system, and predatory lending practices, have created a situation where the vast majority of credit users are extended far beyond their means. The over-extension of credit fueled the post WWII suburban boom by marketing the “American dream” as involving home (or land) ownership, the white picket fence, and so on. While the dream of homeownership and the white picket fence have become engrained in our culture, only those individuals with particular means are able to actually obtain these commodities.

Due to the development of new highly differentiated modes of production, government financing, relatively low interest rates, and high real wages, housing became affordable to more families, spurred economic development on the fringe of the urban center, and drove the process of neighborhood succession. The effects of neighborhood succession created a “hole” where the central business district used to be. The recent immigrants soon found themselves surrounded by dilapidated housing and devoid of the resources that would provide them with an adequate means of subsistence. The process of neighborhood succession created an increased interdependence among residents through industrial development, but also increased

the alienation of these residents from the rest of the economic, social, and political processes necessary for a healthy urban center.

Social Exploitation

Capitalism has effectively reduced our social relationships to contracts based on money. The invasion of the money economy into our social lives is quite profound. The resulting inconsistencies between actual productive and social value and perceived productive and social value in the market system has led to a breakdown in social cohesion. Suburban sprawl, racism, ethnic segregation, labor exploitation, and negative ideological underpinnings created conditions where it was harder and harder for inner city dwellers to obtain the resources needed, causing urban crime rates to soar. The rise in these rates demonstrates the social alienation that manifests itself through capitalist practices. The rise of the money economy has created social conditions where individuals will go through great lengths to obtain it, including breaking laws.

The effects of suburban sprawl had significant impacts on the urban environment. Fuelled by capitalism, the once grand estates that formed the center of activity in the inner city were abandoned for the illusion of things greater like open green spaces, and fresh air. Many of the post industrial mansions of the inner city were boarded up, torn down, or converted into multifamily tenements. It is particularly the latter that had the most profound impact on urban social development. As demonstrated earlier in this chapter, housing prices and location commanded control over social relationships. Poor immigrants were forced into the lowest

substrata of the housing market where they suffered from deplorable conditions, over crowding, and rent exploitation. These sub markets oftentimes existed near industry and transportation lines, where individuals were forced to contend with pollution, noise, and over crowding.

Bell (2009) notes the prevalence of environmental racism in urban centers pointing to two early studies where minorities were more likely to be victims of environmental racism. First, in 1992, the United Church of Christ's Commission for Racial Justice (UCCCRJ) conducted studies based on zip codes and found that "African Americans and other people of color were two-to-three times more likely as other Americans to live in communities with commercial hazardous waste landfills" (Bell 2009:118). The second study in 1992, found that "3% of all Whites and 11% of all minorities in the Detroit region live within a mile of hazardous waste facilities- a difference of a factor of nearly four" (Bell 2009:118). Similar studies conducted in the wake of the 1990's environmental justice movement have shown similar results. In all, 27 empirical studies between 1998 and 2007 demonstrated that "9 found race to be significant, 7 found social class to be significant, and 11 showed that both race and class were significant factors" (Bell 2009:118) in environmental racism.

Social death refers to the breakdown of socio-cultural normative processes and social integration with the greater community as a whole. This includes not only close relationships with family members, co-workers, as well as, broad relationships with higher institutions deemed necessary to maintain social control of the urban environment, i.e. schools, religious establishments, and law enforcement agencies.

All four of the theoretical perspectives previously mentioned can explain the social death of the urban environment.

Group affiliation, or the shared norms and values associated with a particular group of people, provides that social backdrop that allows for normative interaction within a generalized sphere known as the community, or on a larger scale, the urban environment. Within this environment, individuals can act, for the most part, on their own free will as long as they stay within the norms and beliefs associated with that sphere. When individuals possess a high degree of social integration in the group, there is less of a chance that deviance will occur. This degree in integration is difficult to maintain however, due to our insistence on individual rights and privacy, which inherently, undermines the collective nature of the community construct.

The concept of social disorganization is largely associated with the “Chicago School” of sociology and associated with the work of W.I. Thomas and Florian Znaniecki, as well as Clifford Shaw and Henry McKay. Social disorganization refers to both an explanation of deviance and a state of society that produces it. Social disorganization emphasized “that society was organized when people are presumed to have developed agreement about fundamental values and norms, with behavioral regularity. Social organization, or social order, exists when there is a high degree of internal bonding to individuals and institutions in a conventional society (DeMelo, 1999).”

When there is a low level of integration within the neighborhood, social disorganization in terms of deviant behavior, is likely to occur. Since those

individuals do not share the same norms and beliefs as the rest of the community, there is little to no vested interest on the part of the deviant individual. This lack of integration, the lack of shared norms and beliefs, provides the deviant individual with an alternate means of sustaining a quality of life that is suitable to their needs, and obtaining the materials necessary to propagate their own self-interests.

When the neighborhood construct becomes aware that there are deviant individuals living among them, neighborhood residents rally against them, and the norms and beliefs that originally caused the reevaluation of norms by the deviant individual, becomes reevaluated by the collective community to 1) express a distrust in individuals who behave in particular ways, and 2) to promote conformity by the rest of the neighborhood so as to prevent more individuals from becoming deviant. Disdain between the individual deviant(s) and the rest of the neighborhood begins to grow. This conflict further enhances the effects of the reevaluation process of the individual, leading to a likelihood of deviant behavior.

The initiation of outside forces by the greater community, in particular capitalism, further limits the individual's ability to make rational choices on how to obtain the commodities they need to survive because the rights of the deviant individual are now superseded by the greater needs of the shared community. Community boundaries are maintained through this process, leaving "pockets" of like-minded individuals spread out through the city.

As more and more people push into the suburbs as a means of escaping the perceived problems associated with the inner city, they inadvertently bring the

problems they are trying to escape with them; just in a different form. The advent of the internet, and other forms of communication, and its subsequent integration into most homes in urban and suburban areas exacerbates the social integration problem. It is now becoming more commonplace to work from home via the Internet to avoid the hassles of commuting back into the urban center. The rise of Internet commerce means that individuals rarely have to leave their home because most tasks can be performed right from their desktops. Groceries can be picked out and delivered, work can be performed, and you can even find an intimate partner via the Internet. While these make life perceivably easier for the urban dweller, it serves to further break down the social integration of the individual to the greater community, and weakens the socio-cultural normative processes necessary to hold an urban environment together.

Ecologically speaking, the distance from the urban center or lack of access to particular resources further intensifies the social death experienced with a particular community. "A very important attribute of a residential location is its distance from the city center, because this distance is a surrogate for social milieu, as well as the age, style and quality of housing units (Rhoda 1977, p. 11)." Further, income status has been shown to have significant effects on residential location decisions, more so than family structure, which was only a prevailing determinant in higher income groups (Rhoda 1977, p. 17).

Classical land rent theory suggests that both population densities and land values reflect accessibility, thereby limiting residential location decisions to a trade-

off between accessibility to city center amenities and reasonably priced low density housing (Rhoda 1977, p. 11-12). Better access to resources and urban amenities and lower population densities usually incur higher rents and land values. Those residents who are forced to live within the urban environment are, therefore, forced to take on not only the problems of the deterioration of their community, but pay for the amenities exploited by the suburban periphery. Competition for space, invasion by the suburban fringe, domination over access to resources, and the successive push of inner-city boundaries, serve to shape the growth and development of the urban environment by limiting the decision making potential of the residents, severing social ties with extra-community organizations, and weakening the communities ability to socially regulate itself.

Political Exploitation

A sound political system of laws is necessary to ensure that individuals maintain their rights to the materials they possess. The government under a capitalist system is the principle means of protecting individual rights. As we have seen, the initiation of force reduces the individual's ability to exercise their right to rational decision making and sustaining one's right to life, property, and contracts.

“...government is the sole possessor of the right to use retaliatory force against those who initiate force...and in a rational society all individuals agree to delegate to the government their right of self-defense, that is, their right to ward off and defend against those who initiate force against them” (CISC, 2007). By delegating this authority over the use of force to an agency, i.e. government, individuals create an

objective means in which to protect their rights. A constitution serves to bind the government to its essential functions, and to eliminate subjective rule by those chosen to represent individuals in the government.

The government uses its ability to form police forces, militia, and a court system as a means of enforcing the protections afforded under the statutes of the constitution. Under a capitalist system, “[individuals] can enjoy a rule of law rather than the rule of men” (CISC, 2007). This means capitalism eliminates the individual’s ability to make rational choices on the procurement of property by allowing the economic market to determine the best course of action, removing individual control; and allows for the permanent existence of state and privately control over individual interests through the exploitation of contracts.

The chipping away of individual rights protected by the constitution, can be explained by capitalist principles. As mentioned before, a strong governmental system is essential for the protection of individual rights. The most fundamental of individual rights is the Right to Life. In recent years, this right has come under close scrutiny, and has systematically been chipped away. A slurry of abortion, capital punishment, and assisted suicide laws, to name a few, have effectively brought the right to life into mainstream political agendas. One can go so far as to say that governmental entities, acting in their own interests, systematically exploit other nations and governments to procure certain ends they deem justifiable.

For instance, the U.S. invasion of Panama in 1989, and the subsequent removal of Panamanian President Manuel Noriega, provides a contemporary

example. In order to secure rights to the Panama Canal, numerous laws were broken by the U.S. and countless human rights violations were conducted, all in the name of protecting the lives of Americans. According to USTrek.org, the [U.S.] government stepped up economic sanctions, reasoning that if Panamanian citizens were deprived of food and medical supplies, they would lose faith in Noriega's leadership and sway the vote toward his opponents (2008). The UN had declared the invasion a “flagrant violation of International law” because in the days after the invasion, 18,000 Panamanians were forced into refugee camps, where they received little assistance from US forces (or the newly-installed US-supported government), 7,000 Noriega supporters were arrested and illegally jailed without due process, and fifteen mass graves were discovered where US troops had dumped piles of civilian bodies (USTrek.org, 2008).

Another inherent political flaw is the capitalist need for imperialism, which underscores the right to life and property. Marxists argue that the unplanned nature of capitalism inevitably overproduces commodities and overuses resources, which leads it to expand its markets into, and drain the resources out of other, less-developed nations. Again, the Marxist principle of the dialectic is inherent in this argument. On one hand, the globalization of capitalist principles is helping to bring third world nations to higher levels of economic, social, and political success; while on the other hand, systematically invading and exploiting the lives of their citizenry.

Ultimately, individuals have given up certain freedoms, under the illusion that the government they trust knows, and is doing, what is best for them. This notion

serves to systematically limit the individuals ability to make certain rational choices for themselves, and leaves the governmental system with ever increasing powers over the citizens they are suppose to be working for and protecting. While much of the time, the American people have voted to give the government certain powers, it has been done so under a vale of secrecy, and ulterior motives. Although most of the officials who run our government have been voted into office by a supporting constituency, the government, under a capitalist system, becomes its own entity, and works much as any other business or industrial entity, by taking on its own ideas for self-preservation and securing the means to necessary for its own survival. Its exploitative nature is concealed under the guises of “the greater good” in order to gain the trust of the populous necessary for its survival.

Theoretical Linkage

Classical conflict theory and neo-classical conflict approaches, along with ecologically based paradigms offer a unique epistemological perspective useful in the analysis of the community. While they are theoretically different, there are underlying themes that link these theories together, creating an integrated model. First, the study of community in simply ecological spatial terms is only providing half of the picture. Human behavior directly affects the urban environment, and this can be demonstrated by the spatial distribution of resources, driven by the needs of the market system over the needs of the individual. Secondly, capitalism, and its inherent exploitation, is the underlying factor that drives urban development, and conditions social, economic, and political perceptions of the individual in relation to their environment. Thirdly,

the rise of the money economy has invaded all economic, political, and social spheres, and reduced exchange relationships to mere money based contracts.

There is no agreement in the literature on how or why urban centers develop. Whether through concentric zones, or through the development of “minicenters,” urban areas serve the unique purpose of bringing together large conglomerations of people and providing them with the means necessary to obtain the materials they need to promote their survival. Urban centers have developed in various ways, but ultimately will collapse under the weight of one overarching principle: capitalism. Fundamentally, capitalism serves to protect individual rights, such as the right to life and the right to property; however, built into the capitalist system are the flaws, which will lead the demise of the urban center, as we know it.

Economically, capitalism is responsible for the exploitation of individuals, and unjust manipulation of the one thing individuals truly own, their labor. Through this exploitation, economic market systems may flourish, but the price that is paid by those being exploited is not enough to sustain this system indefinitely. The fundamental flaws built into the capitalist economic system had been shown to be particularly destructive to the individuals to whom it is supposed to be helping. The current division of labor, the ever expanding disparity between the owners of the means of production, and those seeking to obtain those means, and the state of the current economy illustrates the growing importance of developing better a economic system in which effective and efficient distribution of goods and services to all individuals is of central importance.

Capitalism also affects the socio-cultural element of urban life. The growing notion of individualism serves to break down the relationships necessary for a health urban environment in two ways: first, by creating an environment of individual alienation from the key components necessary for a health urban environment, i.e. working from home via the internet, and the reliance on external forces to deliver goods and services; and secondly, by systematically unraveling the healthy relationships necessary to sustain integration with the urban construct as a whole, thereby maintaining the moral health of the urban center, and perpetuating class consciousness.

Politically, capitalism has been just as harmful. A strong governmental foundation is necessary to support capitalism. By under cutting the basic principles of the right to life and property inherent in a capitalist system, economic and governmental systems have circumvented these rights, and use them against its constituency in order to propagate its own self- interests. Governments do this by exploiting the notion of the “greater good” and “market stability” to chip away at individual rights, and remove the ability of individuals to make rational choices for themselves.

In the process of market growth under a capitalist system, urban centers act as indicators of the overall health of the market system as they are the primary means by which resources are distributed to individuals. In the face of a floundering national economy, many urban centers have already experienced tremendous difficulties in resource distribution, and there are many more to come. The solutions being proposed

to help these ailing centers are simply band-aids to the problem. Unless a better economic system is implemented and stringently maintained, capitalism will lead to profound declines in American urban stability.

Hypotheses

These underlying themes will be explored in the proceeding chapter through an analysis of Cincinnati's growth and development, and the role capitalism played in shaping and perpetuating the decay of the urban structure. Urban decay will be measured in terms of economic, social/demographic, and ecological dimensions. Using these dimensions, supported by the integrated ecological-conflict theoretical model, we can begin to understand not only why urban decay is occurring, but how economic and social processes are ecologically manifested. Each of the three dimensions will be analyzed independently, as well as cross dimensionally to provide an overall indication of the health of the city. When measuring urban decay, we expect to find breakdowns in family structure, disproportionate incomes along racial lines, and variations in housing patterns from both social and economic perspectives. Specifically, the following relationships are expected:

Economic

Along the economic dimension, it is expected that there will be both spatial and correlational relationships as follows:

- Due to historical suburbanization processes, neighborhoods with higher median rents are expected to be associated with higher median incomes than neighborhoods with lower median rents, and will be

located along the outer reaches of the city limits or along the river front where development is occurring.

- Due to developmental processes, neighborhoods with higher instances of public financial assistance are more likely to be positively correlated with neighborhoods featuring higher unemployment rates than neighborhoods with less public assistance, and will be concentrated toward the center of the city along transportation corridors and be adjacent to Brownfield areas.

Social/Demographic

Along the social/demographic dimension, spatial and correlational relationships are expected to be found as follows:

- Due to the historical process of suburbanization, more sparsely populated neighborhoods are more likely to consist of a higher number of non-family households than more heavily populated neighborhoods, and be located within the inner city.
- Due to historical processes of ghettoization discussed previously in another chapter, African Americans neighborhoods are expected to have higher crime rates and will be concentrated in the inner city, along major transportation corridors, and adjacent to Brownfield Areas than non-minority neighborhoods.

Ecological

Along the ecological dimension, spatial and correlational relationships are expected to be found as follows:

- Due to historical developmental processes, neighborhoods with a higher number of vacant housing units will be more likely to have a shorter commute to work than neighborhoods with lower numbers of vacant housing units, and will be located along the inner city highway corridors and Brownfield areas.
- Due to historical suburbanization processes, neighborhoods with a higher proportion of renter occupied housing units will be associated with the use of public transportation than neighborhoods with lower proportions of renters, and will be concentrated in the inner city, along transportation corridors, and adjacent to Brownfield Areas.
- Due to historical developmental processes, neighborhoods with a higher number of renter occupied housing units without access to phone services are expected to be associated with owner occupied housing units than neighborhoods with lower numbers of renter occupied housing units without access to phone service, and will be disproportionately concentrated in the inner city and along transportation corridors and adjacent to Brownfield sites.
- Police Stations, Fire Stations, Post Offices, and Libraries will be disproportionately located along the outer reaches of the city

Cross-Dimensional

Along cross dimensional lines, spatial and correlational relationships are expected as follows:

- Due to the historical process of ghettoization as discussed earlier in another chapter, neighborhoods with a higher number of residents in poverty will more likely be negatively correlated with neighborhoods featuring a large household size than neighborhoods with a lower number of residents in poverty, and be located within the inner city and along transportation corridors and adjacent to Brownfield areas.
- Due to historical suburbanization processes, neighborhoods with a higher number of renter occupied housing units are more likely to be associated with non-family households than neighborhoods with lower numbers of renter occupied units, and be located within the inner city and along transportation corridors and adjacent to Brownfield areas.
- Due to historical developmental processes, neighborhoods featuring higher median rents are more likely to be associated with the number of people who drive alone to work than neighborhoods featuring lower median rents, and will be located along the outer perimeter of the city.

The next chapter presents a description of how each of these hypotheses is tested against the presented theoretical framework using spatial and correlational analysis.

CHAPTER 3:
METHODS AND RESULTS

The analysis of Cincinnati was broken into two sections: a spatial analysis and a correlational analysis. The methodological components for each section are broken down independently as they were analyzed, and a more general discussion on the overall results of the finding will be discussed in the next chapter. In general, the data set presented is small in size than the original master set for manageability. Numerous economic and social/demographic variables (median rent, median income, households receiving public assistance income, unemployment, non-family households, total population size, African American, poverty, average household size) were taken from the 2000 General Census, Summary File 1 (SF-1 100%), and ecological characteristics (vacant housing units, mean commute to work, renter occupied housing units, people using public transportation, renter occupied units without access to phone, owner occupied housing units, and number of people to drove to work alone) were taken from Summary File 2 (SF-2 100%), all at the census tract level. The full list of variables can be found in table 1.0 in the appendix.

All variables were then weighted and aggregated to the statistical neighborhood level. The Cincinnati Metropolitan Statistical Area (MSA) contains 48 neighborhood designations (N=47). Various neighborhoods were collapsed into larger neighborhood designations for statistical continuity. Pendelton was collapsed into the Over-The-Rhine data; O'Bryonville was collapsed into the East Walnut Hills data;

East Westwood was collapsed in Westwood data; The CUF (Clifton, University Heights, and Fairview) were collapsed into one data set. Since Norwood, St. Bernard, and Golf Manor have their own police force and keep independent crime records, they were excluded from the data set because crime data was not available at the census tract level and are not recognized as being part of CMSA proper.

Analysis 1: Spatial Analysis

Key variables indicating core economic, social/demographic, and ecological dimensional processes were reduced to a manageable size and maps were created to reflect either the highest or lowest 5 scores per given neighborhood. All maps may be found in the appendix.

The first dimension, economic characteristics, contains maps for the variables of median household income, poverty status, unemployment, median household rent, and public assistance income. Median household income and median household rent were weighted to account for differences in census tract size.

Maps were created to represent the second dimension, social/demographic characteristics, contains the key variables of race (African American), total population, nonfamily households, and mean total crime rates (weighted mean of the total Part 1 crime rates of homicide, rape, robbery, assault, burglary, theft, and auto theft aggregated to the neighborhood level).

The third dimension, ecological characteristics, contains maps of key variables including vacant housing units, renter occupied housing units, mean commute to work in minutes, and renter occupied units without access to telephone

service. The variable of mean commute to work was weighted to account for differences in census tract size.

Each of these variables were mapped according to the top five scores in each variable from high to low (or low to high), indicated by the appropriate sequence of color (red, orange, yellow, green and blue). Median rent was also mapped from low to high, along with median household income (lowest being red, orange, yellow, green and blue). Patterns in location of each of the five scores were then analyzed.

Brownfield sites and highway transportation corridors (map produced by the city of Cincinnati) were used as an overlay and applied to each of the previously mentioned maps. A final pattern comparison was then conducted on all of the maps as a whole. Maps including police stations, fire stations, post offices, and libraries were also included for analysis to serve as indicators for access to community services but were not used in the correlational analysis. The results of the analysis are presented in the next chapter.

Analysis 2: Correlational Analysis

Descriptive statistics for the data set can be found in table 1.0 in the appendix. Correlations were conducted on the three variable dimensions. Results of the analysis are presented and discussed in the next chapter. The first, or economic dimension, included the following variables: weighted median household income, poverty status, employment, unemployment, weighted median rent, households receiving public assistance income. The entire correlation matrix for this dimension can be found in table 1.1 in the appendix.

The second, or social/demographic dimension, included the following variables: total population size, race (White, African American), average household size, family household, nonfamily household, and total crime mean. The correlation matrix for this dimension can be found in table 1.2 in the appendix.

The third, or ecological dimension, contains the following variables: vacant housing units, owner occupied housing units, renter occupied units, weighted mean commute to work in minutes (further broken down into drove alone, carpoled, and public transportation), total housing units, renter occupied housing units without access to phone. The correlation matrix for this dimension can be found in table 1.3 in the appendix.

Results

Spatial Analysis

As expected, there were very clear patterns that emerged based on the spatial analysis indicating urban decay. Using the maps to compare the spatial patterns to the individual hypothesis, I can show support for, and at least partial support for, the previously proposed relationships. The findings of the spatial analysis are as follows by their corresponding dimension:

Economic

- The hypothesis is supported because neighborhoods with high median rents are indeed located along the outer edges of the city limits (in no specific pattern) or along the river front where development is occurring

as predicted. Neighborhoods with lower median incomes are also concentrated within the inner city.

- The hypothesis is partially supported because neighborhoods with more household receiving public assistance are concentrated along transportation corridors and near Brownfield areas; however, they are not concentrated within the inner city region. They are generally distributed throughout the city.

Social/Demographic

- The hypothesis is supported because neighborhoods featuring higher numbers of non-family households are generally clustered within the inner region as predicted. Neighborhoods featuring higher total populations are also generally distributed along the outer perimeter of the city.
- The hypothesis is not supported because neighborhoods featuring a higher African American population are not concentrated within the inner city as expected. These neighborhoods are spread along outer portion of the city in 2 specific clusters. Total crime rates did cluster within the inner city along transportation corridors and Brownfield areas as predicted. The neighborhood of Avondale stood out as it received high scores in each variable.

Ecological

- The hypothesis is partially supported because neighborhoods featuring a

higher number of vacant units did cluster within the inner city and did fall along transportation corridors and are adjacent to Brownfield areas as expected. There was also a cluster of neighborhood within the inner city region that had longer commute times, which was unexpected.

- The hypothesis is partially supported. Neighborhood with higher numbers of renter occupied housing did tend to be located near transportation corridors and Brownfield areas; however they were not concentrated within the inner city. Neighborhoods featuring higher numbers of persons using public transportation were not specifically clustered within the inner city which was unexpected.
- This hypothesis is supported because neighborhoods featuring higher numbers of renter occupied units without access to phone service are adjacent to Brownfield areas and transportation corridors, and are clustered within the inner city. Neighborhoods featuring higher numbers of owner occupied housing were located along the outer perimeter of the city as predicted.
- This hypothesis was partially supported. In general, there is a pretty even distribution of municipal service around the city. There is some evidence of clustering, but nothing specifically noteworthy. Further analysis is needed.

Cross-dimensional

- The hypothesis is partially supported because neighborhoods featuring a higher number of residents in poverty were not clustered downtown as expected; however, they were located along transportation corridors and were adjacent to Brownfield areas. Neighborhoods featuring larger household size are also located near transportation corridors and are adjacent to Brownfield areas, and are not specifically clustered within the inner city.
- The hypothesis is supported because neighborhood featuring a higher number of renter occupied housing is closely associated with transportation corridors and Brownfield areas and is generally located within the inner city region. Non-family households are also clustered within the inner city and located near transportation corridors and Brownfield areas.
- The hypothesis is supported. Both neighborhoods with higher numbers of people driving alone to work and higher median rents are located along the outer limits of the city; however they are not the same neighborhoods.

Correlational Analysis

Economic (Table 1.1 in appendix)

- The hypothesis for median household income and median rent was supported as indicated by a positive correlation ($r = .696$), and statistical significance at

the .01 level.

- The hypothesis for unemployment and public assistance households was also upheld as indicated by a positive correlation ($r = .298$) and statistically significant at the .05 level.

Social/Demographic (Table 1.2 in appendix)

- The hypothesis on population size and non-family households was not supported. Total population size was positively correlated with non-family households ($r = .073$) and was not statistically significant.
- The hypothesis on African Americans and crime was not supported. There was a positive correlation between African Americans and mean total crime rates ($r = .172$); however, it was not statistically significant.

Ecological (Table 1.3 in appendix)

- The hypothesis on vacant housing units and commute to work was not upheld. Vacant housing was positively correlated with commute to work ($r = .023$), and was not statistically significant.
- The hypothesis on renter occupied housing and use of public transportation was not upheld. Renter occupied housing was positively correlated with use of public transportation ($r = .017$), and was not statistically significant.
- The hypothesis on renter occupied housing units with no access to phone service, and owner occupied housing units was not upheld. The relationship was negatively correlated ($r = -.574$) and was statistically significant at the .01

level.

- No correlational analysis was run on the fourth hypothesis under this dimension. Rather, the maps were used for spatial analysis only.

Cross-Dimensional (Table 1.4 in appendix)

- The hypothesis on poverty and average household size was not upheld. There was a positive correlation between poverty and average household size ($r=.074$) and was not statistically significant.
- The hypothesis on renter occupied housing and non-family household was upheld. There was a positive correlation ($r=.535$) and was statistically significant at the .01 level.
- The hypothesis on the relationship between neighborhoods with higher median rents and those who drove to work alone was upheld. There was a positive relationship ($r=.856$), and was statistically significant at the .01 level.

CHAPTER 4:

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Discussion

In general, most of the hypotheses presented in this research were upheld with spatial and correlational analysis. The following section will be broken down into a discussion on each dimension, followed by a discussion on the cross-dimensional portion. These sections will then be followed with a general discussion of the research and a section geared toward limitations, implications of the data, and future work, and conclusions.

Economic Dimension

In general, each of the hypotheses was upheld spatially and correlationally. Neighborhoods with higher proportions of median income and median rent are disproportionately located along the outer reaches of the city. This finding is consistent with historical suburbanization processes, and spatially demonstrates the disparity in housing and income. Contrary to what was predicted, neighborhoods featuring a higher number of residents receiving public assistance incomes are not concentrated within the inner city. They are generally distributed across the city, with a small grouping along the I-71 corridor. This could potentially be due to city policy. For example, financially based voucher programs allow lower SES persons to move

to out lying areas by subsidizing the rent for the displaced household.

The spatial analysis clearly shows that economically challenged neighborhoods are not an inner city problem. Quite the contrary, economically challenged neighborhoods are located within close proximity to those featuring generally higher median rents and incomes.

Social/Demographic Dimension

In general these hypotheses were generally not supported or weakly supported both spatially and correlationally. It was generally expected that lower numbers of non-family households would be located further away from the inner city, and indeed that is not the case according to this analysis. The distribution of non-family household along the outer reaches could potentially a breakdown in neighborhood social stability, specifically, the family unit. There are several factors that could be contributing to this pattern, including higher rates of cohabitation or higher rates of split-mortgages, meaning 2 or more unrelated parties sharing the costs of a mortgage in a mutually beneficial arrangement. Additional research would be needed to flush out additional relationships along these lines.

The myth of African American neighborhoods is shown to be both spatially and statistically discredited. Neighborhood with a higher number of vacant housing units would serve as a better predictor of crime, along with several other variables. Additional research along racial lines could potentially flush out the underlying dynamics behind the new “minority-flight” (as opposed to “white-flight”) away from neighborhoods with higher rates of crime.

Ecological Dimension

Most of the hypotheses presented in this section only roughly supported the expected patterns; however, some very interesting patterns did emerge.

Neighborhoods featuring higher numbers of vacant housing are not an inner city issue, except in that they are typically located along highway corridors and Brownfield areas. The recent housing market trouble could be a leading factor in this development. Neighborhoods along the outer suburban areas are developing larger numbers of abandoned single family homes.

The relationship with commute times was also interesting. Historically we are led to believe that suburbanites have longer commutes because of the trip to their inner city, business district jobs. This did not seem to be the case according to the spatial analysis, and in fact, the opposite. Some inner city neighborhoods are experiencing longer commute times; potentially do to the suburban flight of commercial and industrial development. From the spatial analysis, we also see that inner city residents are not the sole users of public transportation. Larger numbers of out belt residents are using public transportation.

It would be expected that the number of renter occupied housing units without access to phone service would be located adjacent to transportation corridors and Brownfield areas; however, it was surprising to find that they were not clustered within the inner city. Again, patterns of suburban housing decay are becoming spatially apparent. It was also interesting to see that there was a generally even distribution of municipal services around the city.

Cross-dimensional

Again the suburbanization notions of larger homes, larger families, and larger incomes not help up according to this analysis. Neighborhoods featuring higher amounts of poverty are typically concentrated near transportation corridors and are adjacent to Brownfield areas, but they are not concentrated within the inner city. They are generally distributed along the outer city limits along with household size. Again contrary to the suburbanization notion, neighborhoods featuring higher amounts of renter occupied housing units and non-family housing units are adjacent to transportation corridors and Brownfield areas' however, they are not concentrated within the inner city. This could be due to the increased production of suburban rental communities.

Neighborhoods featuring higher numbers of people to drive alone to work are located on the outer limits of the city along with neighborhoods with featuring higher median rents. This would support the suburban commuter notion that was developed in a previous chapter.

General Discussion

In general, the spatial and correlational analysis supported the aim of the research, in that it was able to spatially and statistically represent the intersection of economic, social/demographic, and ecological capitalist processes. Further, the design of the research allowed statistical linkage within and across the 3 dimensions. This research lends evidence to the notion that ideological and material (or socio-economic and ecological) concepts are dialectically linked, and must be studied in conjunction

with one another. Urban residents can no longer allow themselves to be removed from their environment. Urban space is intrinsically linked with socio-economic development. As long as suburban ideological notions of NIMBY (Not In My Back Yard) are maintained, urban decay will be allowed to further chip away at the stability of the urban environment.

With the linkage of these dimensions, it becomes both statistically and spatially evident that capitalist principles perpetuate urban decay, creating pockets of underdeveloped areas. Neighborhoods that are distressed are starting to move successively and invasively outward, creating opportunities for competition and domination between suburban neighborhoods. No longer is the inner city able to confine the ills associated with industrial (or de-industrial) capitalist development.

Limitations, Implications of the Data, and Future Research

One of the major limitations of this research is the age of the data. The data collected is from a reputable source, but it is nearly 10 years old. This does bring about interesting implications for extending this research. With the publication of the 2010 census, the same data could be collected and used to compare the changes in the patterns over time. This would provide a better understanding of the health and development of the urban structure.

Another limitation to the research is associated with the variables themselves. Because of the aggregation of data from the census tract to neighborhood levels, ecological fallacies are of concern. Statistical procedures can be employed to

minimize the occurrence of such faulty data. Having census tract level data does, however, lend itself to comparison across cities, as well as providing more accurate spatial patterns. More accurate measures could be used to specifically target identified process. Additional research with these variables could produce a series of measures that could be used to create what I will term an Urban Health Index (UHI). This UHI could then be used to spatially and statistically test the health and development of the urban structure. Having the three specific dimensions, combined with cross-dimensional analysis, would provide a useful tool in combating the negative effects of capitalist processes.

The spatial mapping element could also be refined to better represent the associated patterns of development. Using more sophisticated mapping procedures, such as GIS mapping, would provide greater insight to the ecological dynamics between neighborhoods, and the urban environment in general. The utility of the spatial maps would easily lend itself to quick analyses of other cities and their spatial development, and those patterns could then be used to gauge urban health and development.

Conclusion

Using classical Marxian and ecological theories provided a unique backdrop for conducting spatial analysis on economic, social, and ecological variables. Urban decay, featuring depopulation, economic restructuring, property abandonment, high unemployment, fragmented families, political disenfranchisement, crime, and desolate and unfriendly urban landscapes, has been shown by this research to not only

be a problem with urban environments, but is encroaching upon the suburban arena in very predictable ecologically based patterns.

The ecological processes of growth (Competition, Invasion, Domination, and Succession) have been shown to be radiating from the inner city outward. Similar to multiple-nuclei models, pocket of urban decay have shown to be prominent within the inner city of Cincinnati, Ohio. The neighborhoods of Westwood/E. Westwood, and Avondale have been shown to be prime indicators of urban decay by consistently being associated with higher poverty, unemployment, instances of public assistance income, renter occupied housing, and many other negative qualities associated with urban decay.

Traditional theories on urban development do not apply to Cincinnati. Contrary to popular ideological notions of suburbanization, Westwood/E. Westwood and Avondale represent an outward growth of socioeconomically depressed neighborhoods from the inner city. This outward growth, as opposed to traditional inner-city v. suburbs, represents the ideological and material disconnect that has been traditionally overlooked. Advancements in communication and transportation that once aided in industrial, social, and physical growth are now causing inner city neighborhoods to fall below acceptable levels of sustainability, while simultaneously allowing higher classes of suburbanites the ability to maintain false ideological impressions of inner city neighborhoods, furthering the growth of urban decay.

The research that was presented was successful in linking the social and economic process with ecological spatial patterns. Using historically based methods,

policy makers and city officials can use this type of research to 1) aid in the identification of neighborhoods featuring prominent features of urban decay, 2) use the spatial analysis to be able to better distribute resources to maintain urban neighborhood health, 3) and as an aid in the ideological transformation from urban/suburban differences, to overall urban solidarity. Until the material and the ideological components of urban decay are recognized as being inexorably linked, the complex urban dynamics of capitalism will continue to force entire neighborhoods to face growing concerns with financial, social, and ecological degradation.

Urban decay has been shown to be a historically based and an ideologically/materially driven process. Using the theoretical framework provided allows for a unique insight as to how modern urban environments developed and are socially, economically, and ecologically decaying. Using this type of research, policy makers and city officials can use both ideological and materially driven policies to counteract the effects the economic market system is having on our cities. Perhaps in recognizing and becoming proactive (as opposed to reactive) to these processes, we will no longer have to see the death of another American city.

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APPENDIX

Table of Contents

Maps

- Cincinnati Metropolitan Statistical Area
- Transportation/Brownfield Overlay
- Median Rent (H-L)
- Median Household Income (L-H)
- Households Receiving Public Assistance (H-L)
- Unemployment (H-L)
- Non-family Households (H-L)
- Total Population Size (H-L)
- African American (H-L)
- Total Crime (H-L)
- Median Commute to Work (H-L)
- Vacant Units (H-L)
- Renter Occupied Housing
- Public Transportation
- Renter Occupied Without Access to Phone (H-L)
- Owner Occupied (H-L)
- Fire Stations
- Libraries
- Police Stations
- Post Offices
- Poverty (H-L)
- Average Household Size (H-L)
- Renter Occupied (Same as Above)
- Non-family Households (Same as Above)
- Median Rent (Same as Above)
- Drove Alone (H-L)

Ecological Models of Community Development

Tables

- 1.0 Descriptive Statistics
- 1.1 Economic Correlations
- 1.2 Demographic Correlations
- 1.3 Ecological Correlations
- 1.4 Cross-dimensional Correlations

The Chicago School and Community Design

Concentric-Zone Theory – Ernest Burgess (1925)

Sector Theory – Homer Hoyt (1939, 1964)

Multiple-Nuclei Theory – C.D. Harris and Edward L. Ullman (1945)

Map of
CINCINNATI

Legend

- Pavement
- SPUR Districts
- Rivers and Streams
- Municipal Boundary

0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 11 12 13 14 15 16 17 18 19 20 21 22 23 24 25 26 27 28 29 30 31 32 33 34 35 36 37 38 39 40 41 42 43 44 45 46 47 48 49 50 51 52 53 54 55 56 57 58 59 60 61 62 63 64 65 66 67 68 69 70 71 72 73 74 75 76 77 78 79 80 81 82 83 84 85 86 87 88 89 90 91 92 93 94 95 96 97 98 99 100
As of 9/20/02

Median Rent (High to Low)

- Mt. Adams \$678.00
- Hyde Park \$665.00
- Mt. Lookout \$596.00
- Hartwell \$539.00
- Sayler Park \$518.00

CINCINNATI

Median Household Income (Low to High)

- Queensgate \$10898.00
- OTR/Pendelton \$10911.00
- Fay Apts. \$11120.00
- S. Cummingsville/Midvale \$11413.00
- English Woods/N. Fairmount \$12188.00

CINCINNATI

Households Receiving Public Assistance Income
(High to Low)

■	Evanston	2442
■	Westwood/E. Westwood	613
■	Avondale	591
■	Winton Hills	588
■	OTR/Pendleton	541

CINCINNATI

Unemployment (H-L)

- Fay Apts. 17%
- Winton Hills 14%
- N. Fairmount/English Woods 12%
- Over-The-Rhine/Pendleton 12%
- West End 10%

CINCINNATI

Total Population Size (High to Low):

- ▣ Westwood/E. Westwood 11%
- ▣ College Hill 7%
- ▣ W. Price Hill 7%
- ▣ Madisonville 5%
- ▣ Mt. Washington 5%

CINCINNATI

African American Population (H-L)

- Fay Apts. 95%
- ▣ Westwood/E. Westwood 94%
- ▣ Bond Hill 93%
- ▣ Avondale 91%
- Evanston 88%

CINCINNATI

Total Crime Mean (High to Low)

■	CBD/Riverfront	2011.40
■	Avondale	1285.20
■	S. Fairmount	1259.60
■	E. Price Hill	1239.40
■	Walnut Hills	1119.90

CINCINNATI

Mean Commute to Work (High to Low)

- N. Fairmount/English Woods 31 min.
- Queensgate 30 min.
- Saylor Park 29.60 min.
- Fay Apts. 29.50 min.
- Winton Hills 29.30 min.

CINCINNATI

Renter Occupied Housing (H-L)

- Fay Apts. 88%
- Winton Hills 87%
- Corryville 76%
- CBD/Riverfront 75%
- CUF/Fairview 72%

CINCINNATI

Public Transportation (H-L)

- Over-The-Rhine 38%
- West End 37%
- Fay Apts. 32%
- Midvale/S.Cumminsville 31%
- Avondale 28%

CINCINNATI

Renter Occupied Without Access to Phone Service (H-L)

Lower Price Hill	22%
Over-The-Rhine/Pendleton	20%
North Fairmount/English Woods	8%
West End	7%
South Fairmount	7%

CINCINNATI

Poverty (High to Low)

- Westwood/E. Westwood 8%
- Avondale 8%
- CUF/University Heights 7%
- E. Price Hill 6%
- OTR/Pendleton 6%

CINCINNATI

Average Household Size (H-L)

- Lower Price Hill 2.92
- California 2.88
- Midvale/S. Cumminsville 2.75
- Fay Apartments 2.74
- Winton Hills 2.65

CINCINNATI

Renter Occupied Housing (H-L)

- Fay Apts. 88%
- ▣ Winton Hills 87%
- ▤ Corryville 76%
- ▥ CBD/Riverfront 75%
- CUF/Fairview 72%

CINCINNATI

Non-family Households (H-L)

- CBD/Riverfront 90%
- ▣ Mt. Adams 78%
- ▣ CUF/Fairview 76%
- ▣ E. Walnut Hills 71%
- Corryville 71%

CINCINNATI

Median Rent (High to Low)

- Mt. Adams \$678.00
- Hyde Park \$665.00
- Mt. Lookout \$596.00
- Hartwell \$539.00
- Saylor Park \$518.00

CINCINNATI

Table 1.0
Descriptive Statistics

Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
MED_RENT_WTD	47	.00	678.01	387.9443	121.29603
MEDIAN_HHINCOME_WTD	47	.00	104494.00	32975.822	19158.22705
HH_WPAI	47	0	2442	220.66	374.552
UNEMPLOY_per	47	.00	16.91	5.1697	3.56429
NONFAMHH_pct	47	.00	89.47	45.4543	16.12635
POPSZ_per	47	.16	11.18	2.1077	2.22084
AfrAmer_per	47	.10	94.82	39.5923	32.20609
Total_CRIME_MEAN	44	44.17	2011.40	535.8027	416.16209
VACANT_pct	47	.00	30.87	10.8347	6.36967
MEAN_COMMWORK_WTD	47	17.00	31.00	23.1598	3.85372
RenterOCC_per	47	.00	88.02	50.3038	17.68820
PublicTranspo_per	47	1.51	100.00	14.3585	16.09773
ROWOPH_per	46	.00	22.33	3.1890	4.33061
OWNEROCC_per	46	.98	86.39	37.5292	20.11066
POV_per	47	.04	7.99	2.1277	2.10935
A_HH_SZ	47	1.16	2.92	2.2132	.42549
DROVEALONE_PER	47	.00	91.88	72.1190	16.28291
Valid N (listwise)	43				

Table 1.1 Economic Correlations

Correlations

		MED_RENT_ WTD	MEDIAN_ HHINCOME_ WTD	HH_WPAI	UNEMPLOY_ per
MED_RENT_WTD	Pearson Correlation	1	.696**	-.180	-.534**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.226	.000
	N	47	47	47	47
MEDIAN_ HHINCOME_WTD	Pearson Correlation	.696**	1	-.204	-.608**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.169	.000
	N	47	47	47	47
HH_WPAI	Pearson Correlation	-.180	-.204	1	.298*
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.226	.169		.042
	N	47	47	47	47
UNEMPLOY_per	Pearson Correlation	-.534**	-.608**	.298*	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.042	
	N	47	47	47	47

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Table 1.2 Demographic Correlations

Correlations

		NONFAMHH_ pct	POPSZ_per	AfrAmer_per	Total_CRIME_ MEAN
NONFAMHH_pct	Pearson Correlation	1	.073	-.094	.332*
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.627	.532	.028
	N	47	47	47	44
POPSZ_per	Pearson Correlation	.073	1	-.087	.008
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.627		.561	.961
	N	47	47	47	44
AfrAmer_per	Pearson Correlation	-.094	-.087	1	.172
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.532	.561		.264
	N	47	47	47	44
Total_CRIME_MEAN	Pearson Correlation	.332*	.008	.172	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.028	.961	.264	
	N	44	44	44	44

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Table 1.3
Ecological Correlations

Correlations

		VACANT_pct	MEAN_COMMWO RK_WTD	RenterOCC_ per	Public Transpo_per	ROWOPH_per	OWNERO CC_per
VACANT_pct	Pearson Correlation	1	.023	.556**	.142	.647**	-.722**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.880	.000	.342	.000	.000
	N	47	47	47	47	46	46
MEAN_COMMWORK_WTD	Pearson Correlation	.023	1	.072	.471**	.471**	-.199
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.880		.632	.001	.001	.184
	N	47	**47	47	47	46	46
RenterOCC_per	Pearson Correlation	.556**	.072	1	.017	.464**	-.964**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.632		.908	.001	.000
	N	47	47	47	47	46	46
PublicTranspo_per	Pearson Correlation	.142	.471**	.017	1	.605**	-.696**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.342	.001	.908		.000	.000
	N	47	47	47	47	46	46
ROWOPH_per	Pearson Correlation	.647**	.471**	.464**	.605**	1	-.574**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.001	.001	.000		.000
	N	46	46	46	46	46	46
OWNEROCC_per	Pearson Correlation	-.722**	-.199	-.964**	-.696**	-.574**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.184	.000	.000	.000	
	N	46	46	46	46	46	46

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 1.4

Cross-dimensional Correlations

Correlations

		MED_RENT_ WTD	MEDIAN_ HHINCOME_ WTD	HH_WPAI	UNEMPLOY_ per	NONFAMHH_ pct	POPSZ_per
MED_RENT_WTD	Pearson Correlation	1	.696**	-.180	-.534**	.433**	.204
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.226	.000	.002	.168
	N	47	47	47	47	47	47
MEDIAN_ HHINCOME_WTD	Pearson Correlation	.696**	1	-.204	-.608**	-.065	.143
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.169	.000	.662	.337
	N	47	47	47	47	47	47
HH_WPAI	Pearson Correlation	-.180	-.204	1	.298*	-.044	.249
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.226	.169		.042	.768	.092
	N	47	47	47	47	47	47
UNEMPLOY_per	Pearson Correlation	-.534**	-.608**	.298*	1	-.023	-.220
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.042		.880	.137
	N	47	47	47	47	47	47
NONFAMHH_pct	Pearson Correlation	.433**	-.065	-.044	-.023	1	.073
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.002	.662	.768	.880		.627
	N	47	47	47	47	47	47
POPSZ_per	Pearson Correlation	.204	.143	.249	-.220	.073	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.168	.337	.092	.137	.627	
	N	47	47	47	47	47	47
AfrAmer_per	Pearson Correlation	-.613**	-.596**	.429**	.592**	-.094	-.087
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.003	.000	.532	.561
	N	47	47	47	47	47	47
Total_CRIME_MEAN	Pearson Correlation	-.117	-.346*	.143	.278	.332*	.008
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.450	.022	.355	.068	.028	.961
	N	44	44	44	44	44	44
VACANT_pct	Pearson Correlation	-.284	-.518**	.169	.519**	.422**	-.218
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.053	.000	.256	.000	.003	.141
	N	47	47	47	47	47	47
MEAN_ COMMWORK_WTD	Pearson Correlation	-.600**	-.369*	.172	.524**	-.559**	.048
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.011	.249	.000	.000	.748
	N	47	47	47	47	47	47
RenterOCC_per	Pearson Correlation	-.193	-.586**	.113	.724**	.535**	-.094
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.193	.000	.450	.000	.000	.529
	N	47	47	47	47	47	47

Correlations

		MED_RENT_ WTD	MEDIAN_ HHINCOME_ WTD	HH_WPAI	UNEMPLOY_ per	NONFAMHH_ pct	POPSZ_per
PublicTranspo_per	Pearson Correlation	-.758**	-.597**	.132	.285	-.285	-.186
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.376	.052	.052	.211
	N	47	47	47	47	47	47
ROWOPH_per	Pearson Correlation	-.605**	-.538**	.151	.604**	.026	-.184
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.315	.000	.865	.221
	N	46	46	46	46	46	46
OWNEROCC_per	Pearson Correlation	.547**	.832**	-.115	-.728**	-.461**	.215
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.447	.000	.001	.151
	N	46	46	46	46	46	46
POV_per	Pearson Correlation	-.255	-.341*	.483**	.356*	.192	.641**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.084	.019	.001	.014	.195	.000
	N	47	47	47	47	47	47
A_HH_SZ	Pearson Correlation	-.318*	.000	.200	.359*	-.642**	-.052
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.029	.997	.177	.013	.000	.726
	N	47	47	47	47	47	47
DROVEALONE_PER	Pearson Correlation	.856**	.720**	-.184	-.438**	.338*	.250
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.215	.002	.020	.090
	N	47	47	47	47	47	47

Correlations

		AfrAmer per	Total_CRIME_ MEAN	VACANT_pct	MEAN_ COMMWO RK_WTD	RenterOCC_ per	Public Transpo per
PublicTranspo_per	Pearson Correlation	.616**	.082	.142	.471**	.017	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.598	.342	.001	.908	
	N	47	44	47	47	47	47
ROWOPH_per	Pearson Correlation	.272	.177	.647**	.471**	.464**	.605**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.067	.256	.000	.001	.001	.000
	N	46	43	46	46	46	46
OWNEROCC_per	Pearson Correlation	-.524**	-.448**	-.722**	-.199	-.964**	-.696**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.003	.000	.184	.000	.000
	N	46	43	46	46	46	46
POV_per	Pearson Correlation	.403**	.275	.271	.297*	.403**	.175
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.005	.071	.066	.043	.005	.240
	N	47	44	47	47	47	47
A_HH_SZ	Pearson Correlation	.069	-.007	.004	.449**	-.060	-.130
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.646	.964	.980	.002	.687	.385
	N	47	44	47	47	47	47
DROVEALONE_PER	Pearson Correlation	-.594**	-.106	-.328*	-.516**	-.126	-.922**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.494	.024	.000	.399	.000
	N	47	44	47	47	47	47

Correlations

		AfrAmer per	Total_CRIME_ MEAN	VACANT_pct	MEAN_ COMMWO RK_WTD	RenterOCC_ per	Public Transpo per
MED_RENT_WTD	Pearson Correlation	-.613**	-.117	-.284	-.600**	-.193	-.758**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.450	.053	.000	.193	.000
	N	47	44	47	47	47	47
MEDIAN_ HHINCOME_WTD	Pearson Correlation	-.596**	-.346*	-.518**	-.369*	-.586**	-.597**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.022	.000	.011	.000	.000
	N	47	44	47	47	47	47
HH_WPAI	Pearson Correlation	.429**	.143	.169	.172	.113	.132
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.003	.355	.256	.249	.450	.376
	N	47	44	47	47	47	47
UNEMPLOY_per	Pearson Correlation	.592**	.278	.519**	.524**	.724**	.285
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.068	.000	.000	.000	.052
	N	47	44	47	47	47	47
NONFAMHH_pct	Pearson Correlation	-.094	.332*	.422**	-.559**	.535**	-.285
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.532	.028	.003	.000	.000	.052
	N	47	44	47	47	47	47
POPSZ_per	Pearson Correlation	-.087	.008	-.218	.048	-.094	-.186
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.561	.961	.141	.748	.529	.211
	N	47	44	47	47	47	47
AfrAmer_per	Pearson Correlation	1	.172	.302*	.387**	.396**	.616**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.264	.039	.007	.006	.000
	N	47	44	47	47	47	47
Total_CRIME_MEAN	Pearson Correlation	.172	1	.422**	.061	.431**	.082
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.264		.004	.694	.004	.598
	N	44	44	44	44	44	44
VACANT_pct	Pearson Correlation	.302*	.422**	1	.023	.556**	.142
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.039	.004		.880	.000	.342
	N	47	44	47	47	47	47
MEAN_ COMMWORK_WTD	Pearson Correlation	.387**	.061	.023	1	.072	.471**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.007	.694	.880		.632	.001
	N	47	44	47	47	47	47
RenterOCC_per	Pearson Correlation	.396**	.431**	.556**	.072	1	.017
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.006	.004	.000	.632		.908
	N	47	44	47	47	47	47

Correlations

		ROWOPH_per	OWNERO CC per	POV_per	A HH_SZ	DROVEAL ONE PER
MED_RENT_WTD	Pearson Correlation	-.605**	.547**	-.255	-.318*	.856**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.084	.029	.000
	N	46	46	47	47	47
MEDIAN_HHINCOME_WTD	Pearson Correlation	-.538**	.832**	-.341*	.000	.720**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.019	.997	.000
	N	46	46	47	47	47
HH_WPAI	Pearson Correlation	.151	-.115	.483**	.200	-.184
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.315	.447	.001	.177	.215
	N	46	46	47	47	47
UNEMPLOY_per	Pearson Correlation	.604**	-.728**	.356*	.359*	-.438**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.014	.013	.002
	N	46	46	47	47	47
NONFAMHH_pct	Pearson Correlation	.026	-.461**	.192	-.642**	.338*
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.865	.001	.195	.000	.020
	N	46	46	47	47	47
POPSZ_per	Pearson Correlation	-.184	.215	.641**	-.052	.250
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.221	.151	.000	.726	.090
	N	46	46	47	47	47
AfrAmer_per	Pearson Correlation	.272	-.524**	.403**	.069	-.594**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.067	.000	.005	.646	.000
	N	46	46	47	47	47
Total_CRIME_MEAN	Pearson Correlation	.177	-.448**	.275	-.007	-.106
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.256	.003	.071	.964	.494
	N	43	43	44	44	44
VACANT_pct	Pearson Correlation	.647**	-.722**	.271	.004	-.328*
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.066	.980	.024
	N	46	46	47	47	47
MEAN_COMMWORK_WTD	Pearson Correlation	.471**	-.199	.297*	.449**	-.516**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.001	.184	.043	.002	.000
	N	46	46	47	47	47
RenterOCC_per	Pearson Correlation	.464**	-.964**	.403**	-.060	-.126
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.001	.000	.005	.687	.399
	N	46	46	47	47	47

Correlations

		ROWOPH_per	OWNEROC CC per	POV_per	A HH SZ	DROVEAL ONE PER
PublicTranspo_per	Pearson Correlation	.605**	-.696**	.175	-.130	-.922**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.240	.385	.000
	N	46	46	47	47	47
ROWOPH_per	Pearson Correlation	1	-.574**	.268	.220	-.773**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.072	.142	.000
	N	46	46	46	46	46
OWNEROC CC_per	Pearson Correlation	-.574**	1	-.382**	.172	.691**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.009	.252	.000
	N	46	46	46	46	46
POV_per	Pearson Correlation	.268	-.382**	1	.074	-.206
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.072	.009		.622	.164
	N	46	46	47	47	47
A_HH_SZ	Pearson Correlation	.220	.172	.074	1	-.080
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.142	.252	.622		.594
	N	46	46	47	47	47
DROVEALONE_PER	Pearson Correlation	-.773**	.691**	-.206	-.080	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.164	.594	
	N	46	46	47	47	47

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).